

**NATIONAL UNION OF ROAD TRANSPORT WORKERS (NURTW) AND
ELECTORAL PROCESS IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA (2015-2020)**

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ABSTRACT

The study identified ways in which the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) informally gets involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria; ascertained the implications of the activities of the NURTW on the electoral process; and investigated whether there was a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different State branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the electoral process. It also examined how the electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening the country's quest for credible election in Southwest, Nigeria. These were with a view to establishing possible nexus between the NURTW and the electoral process.

Data for the study were gathered through primary and secondary sources. Primary data were sourced via in-depth interview of 50 Key Informant Respondents (KIRs), which comprise personnel from the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) and National Union of Road Transport Workers (NUTRW), some academics in relevant disciplines from Nigerian universities, card carrying members of the All-Progressives Congress (APC) and the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP) as well as commuters and electorates. Secondary data sources included books, journal articles, online publications, newspaper editorials, published and unpublished dissertations and via the internet. The data gathered were analysed through thematic analysis.

The study revealed that NURTW informally gets involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria, through the provision of logistics services such as transportation of election materials. Also, the study established that the involvement of the NURTW in the electoral process enhanced hitch-free conduct of elections. The study found that the nature of the transport union in the Southwest vis-à-vis its leadership structure and modes of operations made it impossible to achieve uniformity in their involvement in elections in the country. The study established that the

use of technology in the electoral process during voters' registration and on the day of election would improve voters' confidence.

The study concluded that the involvement of the NURTW in the electoral process through the provision of logistics services contributed towards achieving successful elections in Southwest, Nigeria.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Liberal democracy, given its core principles, which include popular sovereignty, periodic election, separation of power, existence of checks and balances, rule of law, fundamental human rights, among other tenets, is arguably one among the systems of government that is most practised in the comity of nations. The reasons are attributed to the position that liberal democracy guarantees, perhaps more than any other system of government, the participation of the citizenry in governance regardless of their background or creed. These roles are manifest in the inalienable rights of the electorates to select their preferred candidate(s) through an electoral process as well as the liberty to demand accountability of their representatives whom they have elected into public offices. Frey (2016: 6) acknowledged that ‘while there is no perfect system of government anywhere in the world, democracy remains a widely practised style of governance due to the degree of rights and privileges it places on the people to determine the calibre of persons that will constitute the government’. He added that:

The practice of democracy is one that allows to a certain degree, the people’s right to decide who controls the machinery of government. Given that democracy places the people at the centre, human values and rights are core values the system upholds. Democracy is far from perfect, but when it comes to running a government, it has a number of built-in mechanisms for promoting fairness and participation (p.7).

Despite the seeming attractiveness of representative (liberal) democracy vis-à-vis its attendant principles, the system is not flawless. Even the United States, adjudged to be one of the oldest practitioners of indirect democracy, has experienced varying controversies (Sandra, 2020). For instance, the Russian government was accused of infiltrating the information systems of the Democratic National Committee (DNC), and the Democratic Congressional Campaign Committee (DCCC) during the 2016 United States presidential elections aimed at boosting the candidacy of the eventual winner, Donald Trump (Kevin, 2019:1). The controversies that also trailed the 2020 presidential election between the Democrat representative and eventual winner, Joe Biden and the immediate past President and Republican representative, Donald Trump leading to the invasion of the Capitol by supporters of the former President over his reluctance to concede defeat premised on his allegation of election rigging, was another factor that exposed some of the challenges of democratic practice in the United States (USA Today, 2021)

De-silver (2019) argued that despite the growing concerns over the practice of democracy in relation to its level of representativeness, the system of government is arguably among the most adopted by countries across the world. This is because democratic principles give room for some level of openness in terms of participation of the people in governance. It enabled the people to enter into a form of agreement with their elected representatives hinged on support for the government in exchange for socioeconomic cum political growth and development. Hence, the admiration for the democratic system is manifest in the number of countries around the world that has embraced it. It is noteworthy that 96 out of 167 countries of the world have adopted some degree and/or strand of democracy (Drew, 2019:3).

At the core of democracy lies the electoral process, which connects and/or brings public office seekers and the electorates together. While the electoral process allows the electorates some degree

of rights and responsibility in determining the make-up of the government, political parties and persons seeking public offices, on the other hand, woo voters. This is because the electorates play a major role during elections. *Encyclopedia Britannica* (2020:3) acknowledges that the electoral process is the heart of democratic practice. Hence, election remains a competitive process that enables the electorates to scrutinize the portfolio and manifestoes of their prospective representatives, thereby allowing them some level of checks on the actions and inactions of public office holders (Britannica, 2020).

Kuhne (2010:1) argues that the electoral process, if properly managed, has the capability to lead a country towards the path of development. In developing countries of the world, especially Sub-Saharan Africa, the electoral process has pushed the region further the path of conflict and instability due to issues associated with electoral malpractices, and other related anti-democratic practices. The electoral process in Nigeria since the return to civil rule in 1999 has been faced with different challenges. These issues, which are traceable to the activities and actions of the political elites, have negatively influenced the country's electioneering and democratization process, so much that some of the electorates have virtually lost confidence in the electoral management body as well as in the leadership of the country (Wilmot, 2019:4). Hence, Osinachukwu and Jayum (2011: 13) note that the electoral process in Nigeria, especially since the return to democratic rule in 1999, has been characterized by different challenges such as voters' intimidation and harassment, exchange of vote for cash, ballot snatching and stuffing, and financial inducement of electoral officials. The implications are evident in the socioeconomic and political crises plaguing the country (Osinachukwu & Jayum, 2011: 15).

Similarly, the electoral process in Nigeria has been controversial, leading sometimes to the cancellation of election results. This is manifest in the varying levels of the election petitions and

court cases contesting the outcome of the electoral process in the country. For instance, following the 2019 general elections, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) had to withdraw 64 Certificates of Return earlier issued to supposed winners and re-issued them to candidates declared victors by the Court (Dele-Adedeji, 2020:1). This included the sacking of Emeka Ihedioha by the Supreme Court, who had been elected as the Governor of Imo State under the platform of the People's Democratic Party (PDP); and his replacement by Hope Uzodinma, of the All Progressives Congress (APC). Another scenario was that of Bayelsa State All Progressives Congress (APC) gubernatorial candidate, David Lyon, who was sacked by the Supreme Court 24 hours to his inauguration as Governor, and replaced with the People's Democratic Party (PDP) candidate, Duoye Diri (Dele-Adedeji, 2020).

Electoral processes in countries like Australia, the United States, Britain, Germany, Switzerland, Canada, among other developed countries of the world that have embraced the principles of democracy, are arguably commendable given the nature of democratisation process over the years (Allan & Burdett, 2002; Schmidt, 2005; Eriksen, Erik & John, 2002); this is not to say that the political system in these countries is perfect. It may be traceable to the roles state and non-state actors played in ensuring the credibility of the electoral and democratic process. One such role is played by lobbyist groups. The lobbyist groups may include interest and pressure groups such as multinational organizations, trade unions, environmentalists, religious organisations, among others. Their roles in the polity, especially during elections, are crucial in determining who takes over the machinery of government. They also advance democratization process through the sensitization and engagement of the electorates on the importance of exercising their civic responsibilities (Allan & Burdett, 2002).

Furthermore, interest and pressure groups play the role of lobbyists in a liberal democratic state aimed at advancing the interests of their members by influencing government policies. During elections, they play the roles of supporters and financiers of political parties and candidates seeking public office; aggregate the interest of the electorates; conduct polls and research aimed at ensuring their candidate(s) emerge winners (Allan & Burdett, 2002).

In the United States, for instance, the National Rifle Association (NRA) is a powerful lobbyist group in the country's politics. The organisation influences the electoral process using its financial capacity and large following to its advantage (*Business Insider*, 2018). It is noteworthy that from 2012 to 2016, about 88% Republican candidates and 11% Democrats received one form of support or the other for election purposes from the National Rifle Association (*Business Insider*, 2018). As a result, the association influences the Congress to adopt policies that promote gun rights. Since 1994, the association has not lost litigation over gun control legislation in the country (Philip, Goss & Kristin, 2014: 198). Similarly, Reich and Barth (2017:485) note that the roles of the NRA in US politics cannot be overstated given its consistency over the years. Hence:

At the core of Political Action Committee (PAC) in the United States, lies the National Rifle Association which doubled as a powerful lobbyist group in the country's politics. During the 2016 elections, the association raised a record of \$366 million, and spent \$412 million, all for political activities (p. 492).

In Europe, with reference to the European Union (EU), Albert and Geiger, a foremost law firm, is regarded as one of the most influential lobbyist organisations on the continent (Albert & Geiger, 2019). The firm is renowned for influencing the policies of the EU using the instrumentality of its membership, which comprises top EU politicians, officials, and attorneys to its advantage (Albert & Geiger, 2019). It may be argued, therefore, that the influence of Albert and Geiger in Europe

may be likened to that of top lobbyist groups in the United States (Newman, Wright & McClenaghan, 2012).

In Nigeria, there exists several interest/lobbyist groups, such as the Nigerian Bar Association (NBA), Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC), Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ), National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), National Association of Nigerian Students (NANS), among others, whose activities influence the democratisation process in the country. However, the role of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) stands out especially as it pertains to the electioneering process (Agbiboa, 2018:7). Though the association exists primarily to protect the interest of transport workers in the country, its influence in the polity cannot be overstressed. Agbiboa (2018) asserts that the leadership of the NURTW arguably plays a key role in determining who emerges as the Governor of Lagos. This is achieved through the influence of the association's structure and membership strength, which spreads across communities in Nigeria (Agbiboa, 2018:6).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Elections serve as a mechanism for selecting public office holders in a state. However, the credibility of the electioneering process is subject of debate across the world. In most African countries, elections are often problematic. In Nigeria, for instance, especially since the return to civil rule in 1999, elections and electioneering processes have been negatively impacted by varying levels of factors such as ballot snatching and stuffing, exchange of vote for cash, voters' intimidation, violence, cancellation of election results by the electoral management body (INEC) among other challenges (Adeniyi, 2006), which often leads to the electorates' loss of confidence in the electoral process.

Omobowale (2008:13) acknowledges that electoral violence remains a major challenge affecting the electoral process in Nigeria. Politicians often use members of interest groups to advance their candidacy. While this is not unconstitutional, some of these interest groups sometimes engage in different forms of electoral malpractice, including the use of violence and intimidation of voters. This is done with a view to boosting the chance of their preferred candidate and political party. There is barely an elected political representative in the Southwestern part of Nigeria who emerged without the influence and support of lobbyist/interest groups, especially the ones that command large following at the grassroots (Omobowale, 2008).

Several studies had been conducted on electoral process in Nigeria. The same cannot be said with regards to appraising the role of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) on the electoral process. Agbibo (2008) contended that appraising electoral process, especially in Southwest, Nigeria, is incomplete without acknowledging the role of the NURTW given the nature of their activities.

While there exists several studies that have examined the role of democracy, elections and interest groups within and outside the context of Nigeria's political space, not many studies have examined the possible relationship that exists between the NURTW, electoral and democratisation processes in Southwest, Nigeria. This study does not claim to provide an exhaustive analysis on the possible relationship between NURTW and electoral process; rather, it unravels the possible influence of the Union on electioneering in Southwest, Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

Arising from the statement of the problem, the following research questions will guide the study:

- i. In what ways does the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) informally get involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria?

- ii. What implications do the activities of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) have on the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria?
- iii. Is there a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different State branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the electoral process?
- iv. In what ways can the electoral process in Nigeria be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening democratic process in the country?

1.4 Research Objectives

The research objectives are to:

- i. identify ways in which the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) informally get involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria;
- ii. ascertain the implications of the activities of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) on the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria;
- iii. investigate whether there is a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different State branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the electoral process; and
- iv. examine how the electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening democratic process in the country.

1.5 Working Assumptions

- i. Violence is the tool often employed by the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) to influence the electioneering process in Southwest, Nigeria.
- ii. The activities of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) during elections promote credible electioneering process in Southwest, Nigeria.

- iii. There is no uniformity of perspective and approach in the way different State branches of the NURTW get involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria.
- iv. Elections in Nigeria rarely reflect the choice of the electorates thereby negatively impacting on voters' confidence as well as the country's quest towards democratic deepening.

1.6 Scope of the Study

Although the study examines the role of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria, the scope of the study is southwestern states of Lagos, Osun and Ondo; with each State representing each of the three axis in Yorubaland/Southwest, Nigeria: Lagos/Ogun, Oyo/Osun and Ondo/Ekiti. The study areas, Lagos, especially were chosen given their cosmopolitan nature and due to the membership strength of the union in the selected Southwest states. These features will possibly enable the gathering of different perspectives on the subject. Agbiboa (2018) argued that the Lagos NURTW chapter, for instance, plays a key role in the emergence of any party candidate as Governor in the State given its membership strengths and popular public transport services.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The study is significant in that it examines the role of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) in the electoral process, specifically, Southwest, Nigeria. Also, the study will add to the existing literature on democracy, election and electioneering process, and the role of interest groups in Nigeria's politics. Additionally, researchers and academics undertaking a study on the subject and its related themes will find the study a useful source of reference.

1.8 Operational Definition of Terms

Accountability: Accountability refers to the process whereby persons who occupy leadership positions conduct their affairs within the domain of the law. Hence, rather than advance sectional interests, such leaders promote the interest of all. For the study, accountability will refer to the rights of the people to enquire into the activities of their representatives in government. This is aimed at ensuring such representatives discharge its duties according to the provision of the constitution, and if found wanting, are made to answer for their misuse of office.

Democracy: Democracy has over the years been ascribed different definitions by scholars of politics. At the core of the system is the role of the people who determine the nature of public office holders to be selected during an election. For the study, democracy will include the tenets of representative democracy such as periodic elections, fundamental human rights, freedom of the Press; and rule of law, among others. It is noteworthy that representative democracy is the most practised system in the comity of democratic states in the world. Touraine (2019) defined democracy as the system that allows the people the right to choose the crop of individuals that will steer the machinery of the state. Further, democracy bestows upon the people certain privileges like freedom of expression, which enables the people to demand accountability of the government, among other rights.

Elections: Elections remain a core component of a democratic system. Election allows the people the rights to choose and/or select the crop of individuals that will make up the government. Adejumobi (2007) notes that election is one of the key principles of a democracy. The reason is that election plays a key role in determining the nature of leaders who will exercise power in government. Further, elections create the avenue where the people examine the records of their leaders aimed at determining the extent to which they have contributed to the growth and development of the country.

Power: The concept of power is often described in the pejorative sense, to mean the ability to compel one to act in ways he/or she ordinarily will not act. For the study, power will refer to the responsibilities vested in an office or position, and the extent to which such position is used to advance nation-building.

Interest Groups: Interest groups will refer to formal and informal organisations that play different roles in a democratic state such as aggregating interests of their members and/or sensitizing the public on government policies as well as influencing government policies. Karr (2007) describes interest groups as firms and organisations whose objectives are largely demonstrated in promoting and protecting the interests of their members, providing some degree of political education to the electorates; financing and supporting political parties. They constitute a core component of the electioneering process in a democratic state. In the view of Diamond (1994), civil societies foster a great deal of limitation on state power by monitoring and controlling the activities of the government.

1.9 Organisation of Study

This study is structured into six chapters. The first is the introduction. Chapter Two reviews the concepts and literature relevant to the research topic. This includes the theoretical framework adopted for the study. The third chapter contains the methodology. Chapter Four examines the history, and evolution of interest groups in Nigeria and their impact on electoral process. Chapter Five is the data presentation, analysis, and discussion of findings. Chapter Six comprises the summary, conclusion, recommendations, and limitations to the study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

The chapter examined studies relevant to the study. This was aimed at identifying the gaps in the literature the study seeks to fill.

2.1 Review of Concepts

2.1.1 Democracy

The concept ‘democracy’ has over the years been examined by different scholars in the field of politics aimed at appreciating its dynamics and relevance in theory and praxis. Despite originating from the ancient Greek-city state of Athens in the 15th century, the practice of democracy is taken to be dynamic in nature given that it allows, to an appreciable extent, certain rights and authority on the people in relation to determining the workings of the state. Accordingly, Cincotta (2007: 33) notes that the practice of democracy remains an age-long system that allows the people the leverage to determine the make-up of the government in terms of leadership composition. Etymologically, democracy is derived from two Greek words: ‘Demos’ and ‘Kratia’. ‘*Demos*’ means people, and ‘*Kratia*’ means government (Cincotta, 2007: 35). While the ancient Greek-style democracy, otherwise, referred to as ‘Direct Democracy’ restricted its scope vis-à-vis participation in governance to only adult males, democratic practice, today, conceived as ‘Indirect Democracy’ gives room for a more complex and/or broader representation (Cincotta, 2007).

Drawing from the above, indirect democracy places authority in the hands of the people who via an electoral process make, at will, their choice of candidate(s) (Hague & Harrop, 2004:39). This position speaks to the roles the people play as major stakeholders in a democracy. However, the invaluable role the people play as stakeholders in the practice of democracy is contestable. This is associated with the challenges that negatively impact democratic practice in some States in sub-

Saharan Africa, evidenced in the quest of some political parties and persons seeking public offices to grab or extend their hold on power. This position was supported by Smith (2003: 1) who argued that democratic practice in Third World countries rarely reflects the will of the people; rather, it is often a reflection of the will of some members of the elites at the helm of affairs. Events that characterise democratic practice and democratisation process in Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and the Middle East are instructive- especially the gross disregard for fundamental human rights of the electorates to select their preferred representatives during elections (Smith, 2003). With regards to Sub-Saharan Africa, electoral process rarely reflects the will of the people. The acclaimed re-election of Yoweri Museveni as President of Uganda in 2021, extending his hold on power to over three decades, and the arrest and intimidation of members of the opposition party, are instructive in understanding some of the challenges associated with politics and elections in Africa.

Steven (2021: 12) noted that while democratisation process in some parts of the Asian continent is improving especially in electoral credibility, with reference to countries like Hong Kong, Japan and Taiwan, similar claim cannot be made in relation to some countries in Africa, Latin America and the Middle East. Democratic process in countries like Uganda, Somalia, Guinea Bissau, Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, Tanzania, Venezuela, Brazil, Iraq, Iran, among others, are largely antithetical to core tenets of democracy. This is manifest in issues such as intimidation of members of opposition parties, undue review of the constitution to give advantage to some political elites aimed at elongating their hold on power, disregard for fundamental human rights, and electoral violence, which are some of the prominent features of the democratic process in these regions.

From the foregoing, it may be argued that democratic governance in the aforementioned regions falls short of the basic tenets of representative democracy. Mahmud (2005: 6) notes that democratic

governance speaks to the ability of the people to decide the nature of leadership of their country; anything short of that gives credence to autocracy.

In China, for instance, the style of democracy may not qualify as representative. This may be traceable to the existence of a dominant political party (Chinese Communist Party), the disregard for fundamental human rights, media censorship, among other practices antithetical to democratic governance (Bell, 2015). This position is, however, contestable especially as no particular country including the United States, regarded as one of the oldest practitioners of democracy, upholds the rights and liberty of all the people. The gross disregard for the right and liberty of African-Americans in the United States manifests in the prevalence of police brutality and racism as seen in the death of George Floyd in the hands of some police officers. The birth and objectives of the 'Black Lives Matter' movement are testament to the fact that the practice of democracy does not necessarily guarantee that all the principles democracy embodies are strictly upheld by the West in comparison with the Republic of China, often regarded as a less democratic state. It is noteworthy that aside from the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), there exists eight (8) non-communist political parties in China. However, the CCP has since its establishment in 1921 dominated political power in the country (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Peoples Republic of China, 2019: 2); the same applies to some countries in the West and other parts of the world which advocates democracy. It is noteworthy that although the United States, Britain, France and Germany practice multi-party systems, their political space and electoral process are dominated by two political parties as is the case of the Democrats and the Republicans in the United States, and the Labour and Conservative parties in Britain. Bell (2015:3) opines that while the Government of China does not condemn the practice of multi-party system, national (periodic) election may not reflect the rights and liberty of the people. Hence, the rights (will) of the Chinese

people do not hold sway in the State. The position expressed by Bell is no doubt contestable following the controversies that characterised the 2016 and 2020 general elections in the United States. The annulment of the Austria's presidential election by the Supreme Court in 2016 over irregularities, is also instructive. It is noteworthy that the election which witnessed the announcement of Alexandra Van Der Bellen, leader of the Greens, as the winner was overturned and re-run election conducted (BBC, 2016).

In Africa with emphasis on Sub-Saharan Africa, though most countries in the region are practitioners of democracy, and hold periodic elections, the will of the people cannot be said to hold sway. Hence, while elections hold periodically, the outcome is often marred by irregularities. Also, the rights and liberty of the people are often not upheld due to the repressive stance of the government on core principles of democracy like peaceful protest and demonstration; demand for accountability; rule of law; fundamental human rights among others. Terngu (2017) states that although Nigeria qualifies as a democratic state, the nature of governance being dispensed is largely autocratic. For instance, the right to peaceful protest and assembly, freedom of expression, and that of the Press are often restricted by the Federal government. A characteristic action of the government, in this regard, sometimes manifests in the arrests and intimidation of persons who speak against the government, disregard for the application of the rule of law, and media censor among other autocratic tendencies (Seun, 2021). Recently, the government of President Muhammadu Buhari ordered the arrest of groups or individuals protesting against police brutality, maladministration and socioeconomic woes of the country at the Lekki Toll Gate in Lagos State (Seun, 2021).

Human rights records in Nigeria is poor due to the autocratic stance of the government especially that of President Buhari whose actions do not tolerate and respect the inalienable rights of the

people as democracy presupposes (Amnesty International, 2020). The government has also been accused of using security operatives to attack and kill peaceful protesters demanding good governance under the aegis of the 'ENDSARS' protest (Cable News Network, 2021). Amnesty International (2020) report shows that Nigeria ranks high in terms of violation of the rights of the people. While there are increased cases of Police brutality, intimidation and harassment, many persons are unlawfully detained by security operatives on the instruction of the government; sometimes disregarding court ruling. The unlawful detention and intimidation of Omoyele Sowore, the convener of 'Revolution Now'- an activist group, which stands against bad governance in Nigeria, and that of Sheikh Ibrahim El-Zakzaky, the leader of the Shiite group, and some of his followers despite court ruling ordering their release, are instances of the weakness of democratic practice in Nigeria (*Premium Times*, 2016; *Premium Times*, 2019).

Huntington (1991:39) maintains that one of the principles that makes a state democratic is to respect the wills and rights of the people. According to Huntington,

Democracy ceases to exist when the rights of the people to select their preferred candidate(s) are taken away through repressive rule, electoral irregularities. Hence, whenever the rights of the people to vote and as well as contest elective positions are non-existent, such country is practicing an authoritarian regime (1991:55).

In the same vein, Schumpeter (1947) submits that the practice of democracy can be said to be existing in a state when the rights of the people to select and demand accountability of their representatives become a core component of governance. Therefore, the representativeness of democracy in praxis is brought to the fore when authority truly stays with the people, such that, they have the right to select and remove from the position of authority, public office holders who fail to do the bidding of the people (Osinachukwu & Jayum, 2011).

Democracy comes with its salient tenets, which differentiate it from other systems of government. Landman (2018:48) identified the key features of democracy to include: sovereignty residing with the people, such that they have the capacity to select without compulsion their desired representatives; periodic elections, which are credible and transparent, evident by the institutionalisation of an independent electoral management body (EMBs); an inclusive government, which upholds the rights and liberties of the citizens; and equality of persons regardless of their social standing or creed. The above tenets of democracy have over the years proven to be problematic in praxis across democratic states. The violence and controversies that trail the credibility of electoral process in Africa are instructive.

It is noteworthy that the United States presidential election has since 2016 been dogged by controversies, thereby casting doubt on the credibility of the election. The climax of these controversies came to the fore following the 2020 election which pitted Donald Trump and Joe Biden. Notably, disgruntled Trump's supporters attacked the Capitol in a bid to express their discontent over the election results. The former President's stance which suggested that the people defend their votes by all means, undeniably impacted negatively on the practice of democracy in the country (British Broadcasting Corporation, 2020:1). However, the former President's claim of electoral fraud was flawed by the Electoral College results (Philip, 2020). The above position gives credence to the flaws inherent in democratic practice, suggesting that there is no perfect political system in the world. Democracy, however, is arguably the most practised system of government given its 'people-centredness' which is contestable in praxis.

2.1.2 Elections

Elections are often referred to as a key aspect of the democratic process. This is because it remains the mechanism through which public office holders are selected to occupy positions of authority. Election is globally recognized as an instrument in the hands of the electorates, and its practice determines the choice of leader that a democratic state will have within a given period of time (Adekunle & Florence, 2011). While emphasising the importance of election in a democratic state, Animashaun (2010: 32) asserts that election is the heart of any democratic process, and as such functions as a mechanism through which the electorates recruit their representatives as well as demand accountability of them. In the views of Adekunle and Florence (2011:3):

Election is the engine room in a democracy. It is the process that allows qualified adult citizens the avenue to make informed choices over who takes over the rein of government. Therefore, it guarantees the recruitment of the persons that will work towards promoting the interests of the people. The uniqueness embedded in the process lies in the ability of the electorate to demand accountability of their representatives. Hence, a democracy that does not vest in the people the right to determine who governs may be likened to an autocratic regime.

While Nnoli (2003) described election as the livewire of the democratic process whose credibility determines the extent to which democratic state enjoys political stability; Diamond, Linz, and Lipset (1989: 532) opined that election and electioneering process create the avenue for persons vying for public offices to compete and persuade voters to their camp using manifestoes and the political party agenda as instruments. Also, election is synonymous to a contractual agreement between the electorate and their representatives. At any point when such contractual agreement is broken, the onus lies on the electorate to recall such representative(s) using the instrumentality of the constitution as a source of reference (Schlozman & Verba, 1987:341). On the contrary, the application of recall process in checking the activities of public office holders is seldom used in

most countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. For instance, the prevalence of leadership weakness in Nigeria among public office holders evidenced in high level of corruption, abuse of office, among others, have not led to the effective use of recall process to demand accountability of government representatives. Nevertheless, the recall process instituted against former Senator Dino Melaye over alleged abuse of office is an indication that Nigerians are gradually waking up to their role of demanding good governance of their elected representatives (Samuel, 2018).

Similarly, Akamere (2001) noted that elections and electioneering process are all-encompassing phenomena. They include activities such as the registration of political parties and electorates with the electoral management body, delineation of constituencies, voting process; and the inauguration of elected representatives. Gauba (2007:61) acknowledged that election transcends the process of selecting candidates into positions of authority. The process is a continuum whose success advances the democratisation process. The quest to deepening democracy in Nigeria is gradually becoming an impossible feat to achieve evidenced in the attitude of some members of the political elites towards the practice of democracy in the country, especially the use of political thugs to disrupt elections, financial inducement of the electorate and electoral officials as well as the unconstitutional party switching that trails the quest to attain political positions in the country. However, the fact that Nigeria's democracy has since 1999 endured without military intervention in its politics is a pointer to the fact that Nigeria's democracy is sustainable.

While election is a core component of the democratic process, ascertaining the credibility of such a process is not free from challenges. In some African countries, with emphasis on Nigeria, elections are often marred by different challenges. The Nordic African Institute (2013) stated that the electioneering process in Sub-Saharan Africa has over the years proven to be problematic, thereby making credible polls far from achievable. The study avers:

Electoral outcomes in Nigeria, Togo, Kenya, Zimbabwe, and a host of other countries in the region have been enmeshed in controversies and violent conflict. While wide-scale rigging is often reported by both local and international observers, some electorates are often compelled to exchange their votes for cash-sum; others are intimidated or harassed. Similarly, members of the opposition parties are sometimes incarcerated or assassinated. The implications are evident in the political unrest that characterizes these regions prior and after the election due to violent clashes between members of the ruling party, the opposition party, and security operatives (p. 3).

In the same vein, Ojakurotu (2009) noted that the leadership crises that have plagued the Nigerian state since the transition to civil rule are pointers to the nature of the electoral process in the country. Many lives are often lost due to violent clashes that take place before, during, and after election. Thuggery, intimidation, and harassment of voters, snatching and stuffing of ballot boxes are chief among the challenges associated with election in the country. 'Due to the loss of confidence in the process, a number of the electorates choose to stay off the polling units on the day of election' (Ojakurotu, 2009:10). This speaks to the inordinate quest of public office holders and persons vying for public position to grab power by all means. The nature of leadership dispensed in Nigeria reflects the far from credible electoral process, which doubles as one of the challenges affecting democratic governance in the country.

Furthermore, Emmanuel (2001:23) argued that the failure of the election management body (EMBs) to ensure that the will of Nigerians hold sway during the conduct of elections has further dampened the trust the people have in the process. Hence, elections are used as tools for oppression and intimidation rather than for the purpose of advancing the democratisation process. As a consequence, Aleyomi (2010) remarked that the outcome of the electoral process in Nigeria is far from being impressive. The reasons include the inordinate quest of political parties and politicians

to take over the reins of government by all means possible. This accounts for the nature of the electioneering process that the country has witnessed since 1999. The crisis that often follows elections in the country has proven to be dire so much that both international and local election observers often pass negative remarks on the process. For instance, the 2019 general election, which was the most recent election in Nigeria, was described as a sham by international electoral observers (DW, 2019:4).

It is noteworthy that international electoral observers during the 2019 general elections reported that the process was marred by varying degrees of systemic failures that require exigent and proactive electoral reforms so as to drive the democratisation process in the country. Similarly, the ‘Situation Room’, which comprises about 70 civil society organisations that monitored the 2019 general elections, described the process as a ‘shambolic and disheartening process’ (DW, 2019).

2.1.3 Interest Groups

The role of interest groups in a democracy cannot be underemphasized. This is because they play key roles in a democracy, such as aggregating the interests of their members, voters’ education (should the need arise during elections), demanding accountability of the government, and working as think-tanks for government among other institutions of the state. Interest groups include trade unions, religious organisations, multinational corporations, among other bodies whose primary objectives seek to influence government policies. Clive (2020:1) suggested that interest groups comprises an organised association of individuals and groups whose core objectives seek to influence government policies, usually, to their favour. Lobbying is arguably a core mechanism employed by interest groups in achieving their mandate. These keep them in constant interaction with the government (Steinberg & Shih, 2012). Mimiko (2017) affirmed that ‘lobbying’ is a

legitimate instrument of democratic process. Lobbying, therefore, refers to the art of getting a government personnel/representative or institution of government to act in a particular way (Mimiko, 2017:136).

In Nigeria, the art of lobbying is often misconstrued. Lobbying in Nigeria's perspective is often used as an instrument to seek favour of a person in position of authority. This will include the giving and collection of bribes among other inordinate acts such as sex, among other concessions. This position was corroborated by Mimiko (2017:137), who submits that Nigerians lobby for any positions especially 'juicy' ones even if they are least qualified for such posts.

The case of Kano State Governor, Umar Ganduje reportedly caught on camera collecting an undisclosed sum of money in dollars from an unidentified government contractor is instructive (Ogundipe, 2018). Also, the case of Farouq Lawan, a member of the House of Representatives alleged to have collected bribe amounting to \$500,000 from a business mogul, Femi Otedola, to have his company, Zenon, removed from the list of companies involved in a fuel subsidy scam, is another instance in this regard (*Premium Times*, 2013; BBC, 2013); the implication of the foregoing is manifest in the degeneracy witnessed in nearly all facets of Nigeria's political space. Interest or pressure groups vary according to organisational structure and objectives. Therefore, these groups are often categorized according to their motivation and mandate which may include among others, economic, human rights and public interest advocacy, trade unions, and professional groups (Chari, Hogan & Murphy, 2010).

Adeyinka and Emmanuel (2014:1) argued that no liberal democratic state can successfully exist without a viable interest group. Although the interest groups make the pursuit of their members' interests their primary objectives, the roles they play in enhancing democracy cannot be overemphasized. These roles are manifest in educating the electorates on the importance of

exercising their civic responsibility through interest propagation and aggregation. Also, they act as a check on the government by demanding accountability (Adeyinka & Emmanuel, 2014). The Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC), the umbrella organisation for most interest groups in Nigeria for instance, is sometimes alleged of failing to demand accountability of the government, evident in its quick calls to suspend or withdraw demands made of the government only to return to making similar demand after a period of time. One would expect that the NLC use the instrumentality of their membership strength and vibrancy in the country to force the government to make viable concessions for the interests of the populace rather than seeking shortfall solutions. For instance, a former governor of Kaduna State, Ahmed Markafi, was quoted to have accused the NLC of always demanding money from the government rather than good governance (Olufusi, 2019:3). This speaks to the extent to which the course of some interest groups in Nigeria does not reflect the will of the people and advance democratisation due to their partisanship (Olufusi, 2019).

Steinberg and Shih (2012) stated that interest groups are as important as political parties in a democracy, in that, as political parties seek to take over the reins of government using manifestoes and the party ideology as tools, so also do interest groups armed with their negotiating and lobbyist expertise pose as a link between the government and the people with a view to promoting the interest of their members and those of the people at large. Therefore, while political parties need the support of the interest groups to achieve their mandate, interest groups need the support and backing of government to achieve their mandate. This brings to the fore the interconnectedness between government and interest groups in a democracy. Hence, there is a high tendency for a political party or candidate(s) seeking an elective position to emerge winner, if he/she enjoys the support of interest groups in the State. The reasons are traceable to the position that interest groups

canvass for support using their membership strength and structure to their advantage (Wolfram, 2019:3).

Trade unions with a large following or membership strength may transform into a political party, such that they field candidates for elective positions. This is with the mandate of guaranteeing the representation of the interest of their members in Parliament. A case in point is the Labour Party in the United Kingdom, which constitutes the official opposition party in the United Kingdom's Parliament having won the second largest number of seats during the 2019 general election (Wolfram, 2019).

The roles of interest groups in the politics of different countries of the world cannot be overemphasized. In the European Union, for instance, Lehman (2003:3) opined that there exists over 15000 lobbyist groups that comprise organisations, lawyers, non-government organisations, among other groups that seek to influence legislation in Brussels. In the United States and the United Kingdom, interest groups play pivotal roles in the workings of the countries' democratic process (Lehman, 2003). They double as financiers of political parties and candidates seeking public offices. Reich and Barth (2017:485) explained that the role of the National Rifle Association in the US politics cannot be overstated given the consistent roles the group has played in the country's political space over the years.

In Nigeria, the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), National Union of Teachers (NUT), Nigerian Bar Association (NBA), among other interest groups, arguably impact the electioneering and democratisation process in the country. These roles take the shape of voters' education through seminars and workshops, electronic and print media, and interest articulation and aggregation. Amani (2019) notes that though the roles played by civil society organizations during elections in Nigeria include interacting with persons seeking elective positions and other

relevant political stakeholders during and after elections, the credibility of the electoral process is usually in doubt, evident in the nature of malpractices such as intimidation and harassment of voters, violence, ballot box snatching, and exchange of votes for cash sums. The Socioeconomic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) is an example of the interest group in Nigeria whose actions influence the government aimed at promoting good governance. The group is renowned for educating the populace on their fundamental human rights as well as charging the governments to tow the right path in their policies and actions (Iriekpen, 2020). Their roles, in this regard, play a key role in Nigeria's quest to democratisation. The Socioeconomic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP), it should be noted, has been critical of the President Muhammadu Buhari's administration, by way of demanding good governance in the face of insecurity, among other socioeconomic crises affecting the country (Iriekpen, 2020). The actions of the group, in itself, plays a part in deepening democratic practice in the country.

Similarly, with reference to Lagos State, Agbiboa (2018:6) established that the leadership of the NURTW plays a key role in determining who emerges as the Governor of the State. This is achieved through the influence of the association's structure and membership strength, which spread across local communities in the State. Also, their members are often alleged to engage in nefarious activities on and before the day of election aimed at guaranteeing victory for the Bola Tinubu-controlled All Progressives Congress (APC) in Lagos State (Agbiboa, 2018).

2.2 Empirical Review

Studies conducted on themes associated with democracy seem to agree that the democratisation process is a continuum. Further, emphasis has been placed on the invaluable roles of elections in a liberal democratic state. This is because elections advance representation in government. Abuya (2012:1) avers that election and electioneering process, especially credible ones, are key to promoting the democratization process and national integration. Hence, the emphasis lies in the rights of the electorates to select without compulsion representatives of their choice. The reason is traceable to the position that a ‘democracy’ that does not respect the sanctity of elections may be likened to autocracy (Abuya, 2012).

2.2.1 Elections and Electioneering Process in Nigeria

While examining the outcome of the 2015 general election in Nigeria with the objective of determining the degree of political participation, Sheriff, Abdullahi, and Kabir (2015) agreed that the general election was very significant given the fact that an incumbent President was defeated for the first time since the return to civil rule in 1999. The study argued that the spate of insecurity in the country especially in the Northeast, armed conflicts in some parts of the country as well as the economic woes the country witnessed under the leadership of President Goodluck Jonathan were some of the major factors that led to the defeat of the now former president and the Peoples’ Democratic Party (PDP) by the opposition All Progressives Congress (APC). The APC since taking over the helms of affairs in Nigeria has performed woefully, occasioned by the prevalence of insecurity, and youth unemployment among the socioeconomic malaise the country is currently faced with.

The study revealed that voting pattern and behaviour during the 2015 general election reflected religious and ethnic affiliation. Further, the study highlighted that political participation and

voters' turnout was poor due to the people's distrust for the credibility of the election as well as due to the fear of possible violence at the polls as a result of the growing level of insecurity across the country.

The study concluded that the 2015 general election recorded the worst turn out in terms of participation of the electorates since the transition to civil rule in 1999. This is a pointer to many factors affecting democratic practice in the country, which makes her democracy problematic. Although the 2015 general election was dogged by different challenges, the outcome of the election brought to the fore the quest of the people for good governance.

Political participation during the 2019 general elections was no different from the 2015 general elections. Adigun (2020:2) while comparing the level of voters' participation between the 2015 and 2019 general elections revealed that voters' turnout in 2015 was 43.65%, while voters' participation during the 2019 elections was 34.75%. This shows a decline in the level of voters' participation during elections in the country. From the foregoing, it can be deduced that the reasons for the increase in voters' participation during the 2015 general elections resulted from the desires of many Nigerians in demanding a change of government led by Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP). It is noteworthy that PDP were in power for 16 years with no significant level of development to show for it. However, the hopes of many electorates were dashed evidenced in the nature of governance dispensed on the watch of the Muhammadu Buhari-led All Progressive Congress (APC). This was responsible for the low voters' participation in 2019 general elections.

The 2023 elections, it may be argued, may serve a test to the level of political participation in the country compared to 2015 and 2019 respectively. However, the stance of some Nigerian youths against the government in the face of the many challenges affecting the country is an indication that political participation and the demand for accountability is improving in the country.

Accordingly, Ogunmodede (2020) subscribed to the fact that the ENDSARs movement was a sign that demand for accountability is gradually taking shape in Nigeria's politics. This will make the 2023 general election significant in the face of the discontent the people have expressed over the nature of governance being dispensed in the country at the present time.

Similarly, Orji (2015:3) noted that in the face of the challenges of insecurity in the country, evident by the terrorist activities of the Boko Haram sect, the success, in terms of the credibility of the 2015 and 2019 general elections, was in doubt due to the varying levels of violence and controversies generated by the two leading political parties: the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP) and the All Progressives Congress (APC), prior to and during election day. This confirms the various levels of electoral malpractices and violence recorded at major polling units across the country. Also, the study argued that since 1999, the contest of elective positions in Nigeria have been characterised by various crises and controversies dictated by the inordinate ambitions of the politicians to control the reins of government. The implication is reflected in the nature and outcome of elections in the country. The position expressed in the study speaks to the need for the overhaul of Nigeria's electoral process and the restructuring of her politics such that the good of all is advanced. This may be achieved through the strengthening of the electoral management body (INEC) to be independent of the whims and caprices of the executive which appoints the chair of the body. Further, the removal of the attraction in elective positions will also act as a check to some of the controversies that characterise the electoral process in the country.

Abuya (2012) examined the role of the judiciary in promoting free and fair elections in Africa. The study argued that while it is not totally out of place for the judiciary to mediate over election-related crisis brought to the fore by cases of irregularities, incessant court cases like the ones that characterise elections, on the continent, serve as stumbling blocks to deepening democracy. This

is so because the court cases and election tribunals may distract the government and its institutions from charting a course for the development of the country. For example, the case of Hope Uzodinma of the All Progressives Congress (APC) eventually emerging as the Governor of Imo State through litigation after finishing in fourth position at the governorship general election is a case in point (Yahaya, 2020). Further, the ruling political party in states in Africa such as Nigeria, Kenya, Ivory Coast, Uganda, Rwanda, Zimbabwe, among others, often exercise supremacy over court and tribunal rulings; reason being that they seek to hold on to power by force. To this end, Mubangizi (2005) stated that respect for judicial pronouncement and human rights are non-existent in some countries in Africa. In Uganda for instance, the study noted that President Yoweri Museveni in a bid to continue his autocratic rule forced the Parliament on many occasions to amend the constitution in his favour. This was done with the objective of making him eligible to contest the election despite the constitutional provision that prevented anyone above the age of 70 years to contest the position of the president.

In Nigeria, the challenges associated with electoral malpractices are undeniably responsible for the many litigations and court rulings that have upturned the results of elections declared by INEC. Dele-Adedeji (2020:1) opined that since 1999, the electoral process has been controversial, leading, sometimes to the cancellation of election results.

Stephanie and Burchard (2019) noted that elections in most countries in Africa are often marred by challenges of electoral violence as experienced in Ethiopia in 2015, Kenya in 2007, Ivory Coast in 2011, Zimbabwe in 2008, and Nigeria since 1999. This negatively impacts on democratic deepening in these countries. Similarly, Lauren (2012) claimed that the economic and political instability plaguing the Nigerian state is traceable to the nature of representatives elected into government by the electorate. The position expressed above is a pointer to the position that some

of the leaders elected to take charge of the machinery of government rather than advance the interest of the people, pursue their selfish interests and those of their party members. In this regard, Albert (2006) cited cases of former Nigerian Governors who served and paid allegiance to their godfathers instead of the electorate. Some of these leaders include Chief Jim Nwodo and Chief Sam Mbakwe, both of whom were former governors in Anambra and Imo States and were godsons of late Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe. Former Anambra State Governor, Dr. Chris Ngige, was also a godson to Chief Chris Uba, who revealed he made him a governor and not just a senator, among others (Albert, 2006).

The study by Peter and Michael (2000), which examined attitudes to democracy and elections in Nigeria, noted that military intervention in the country's political space negatively impacted the country's development. The study established that the adoption of democratic practice seems suitable to the country's population size and economic strength. Relying on the 1999 general election, which led to the emergence of Olusegun Obasanjo as the President of the country after decades of military rule, the study contended that if the controversies that surrounded the 1999 general elections were checked in the coming years, they will act as catalyst that will promote democracy and democratisation in the country. While the positions expressed by the authors are valid, attaining credible elections in the country may be a difficult feat to achieve. This is premised on the attitudes of public office seekers towards politics and by extension, elections in Nigeria. This is as a result of the many attractions attached to political positions in Nigeria. It is noteworthy that Nigerian politicians are ranked among the highest paid and the wealthiest compared to their counterparts across the world (Italoye, 2020).

Adekunle and Florence's (2016) study, which examined credible elections, establishment, and maintenance of democratic order in Nigeria, noted that credible elections remained the

bedrock in consolidating democracy. Further, the study averred that credible elections greatly improved the confidence of the electorates and support for the electoral management body (EMBs) as well as for the elected representatives, thereby advancing sustainable development. The study revealed that election and electioneering process in Nigeria had not been credible due to factors such as thuggery, violence, ballot box snatching and stuffing, bribes, and kickbacks offered to electoral officers and other stakeholders. The implication reflects in the inordinate quest of the political elites to attain political power at the detriment of the populace. The study concludes that rather than developing, the Nigerian state is enmeshed in wanton degeneracy that stifles the democratisation process in the country. Electoral malpractices remain the main challenge stifling the deepening of democratic practice in the country. Issues associated with thuggery and acts of violence underscore the socioeconomic crisis affecting the country. This makes it easy for persons, especially the youths, to be bought over and made to cause havoc prior and during the election for meagre money.

The Nordic African Institute (2013) reports that electoral malpractices are predominant in developing countries whose political space is characterised by poor governance, partisanship, exclusionary politics due to the fear of losing/ceding power to opposition parties. Further, the study argued that violence associated with elections is pronounced in sub-Saharan Africa. These countries rank high in terms of high unemployment rates, illiteracy, low per capita income with decaying socio-infrastructure facilities. Similarly, violence associated with elections, according to the study has led to the death of many, due to clashes by opposing groups and political parties. The study concludes that until structural changes are initiated; the ones that will drive development countries in Sub-Saharan Africa will remain perpetually underdeveloped (Nordic African Institute, 2013:56).

The positions expressed above (Nordic African Institute) is no doubt the reflection of politics and democratic practice in not just sub-Saharan Africa but the continent at large. There are rarely any states in the continent where elections are conducted without different controversies such as violence, oppression and suppression of opposition parties and the arbitrary review of the constitution to favour some political elites (especially elites who have held on to political power over a long period of years), exchange of votes for money, etc. The outcomes of elections in Nigeria, Uganda, Kenya, Liberia, Zimbabwe, Mali, South Africa, Cote D'ivoire, among other states in the continent is instructive. The implication manifests in the nature of governance being dispensed on the continent.

2.2.2 Politics and Democratisation in Nigeria

Politics and the democratisation process in Nigeria have since the First Republic been negatively impacted by challenges that threatened national cohesion and development. Prior to military incursion in the country's political space, the federal system of governance, which gave the regional governments of the West, Mid-West, North, and the East the political power to govern the disparate regions without the federal government meddling in their affairs played a key role in promoting economic development in the country. However, crises which resulted from politics and democratisation process such as the Action Group crisis of 1962, the general election and census crises of 1962/1963 and 1964 respectively, among other events that heated up the polity at that time, were the reasons the military junta gave for its intervention in the country's politics.

Economically, the federal arrangement gave the regions the impetus to control resources in their regions amounting to about 50%, while royalties were made to the federal government. This promoted healthy economic rivalry through agricultural production and exports. While the

Northern Region farmed groundnut and cotton in commercial quantities, the West, East, and the Midwestern regions cultivated cocoa, oil palm, and rubber respectively. However, the military disrupted the political arrangements in a bid to promote its interests (Enimue, 2006:23). The position expressed by the author about the role of the military involvement in Nigeria's politics aimed at promoting its interest is contestable. One of the key objectives for military intervention in Nigeria's politics was to restore normalcy in the polity due to the crisis such as the Action Group crisis of 1962, the census crisis of 1962/63 among other tensions on the rise in the country, and not necessarily a selfish agenda as the author (Enimue, 2006) suggested.

While the discovery of oil posed a challenge to the military government that concentrated largely on oil exploration, agricultural production was not totally abandoned. The implementation of the 'Operation Feed the Nation' policy is instructive. Mohammed (2015) noted that democratisation is a continuum (vis-à-vis its adoption and enshrinement in the polity) in a democratic state, which takes the conscious efforts of all and sundry (the governors and governed) to make its institutionalisation a success such that its principles become a way of life for the people. Democratic process in Nigeria is far from being deepened, and this is evident in the absence of rule of law, the flagrant abuse of fundamental human rights, and far from credible electoral process that characterises the country's democracy (Mohammed, 2015:25). The case of Omoyele Sowore, a political activist and convener of the 'Revolution Now' movement, intimidation of protesters demanding good governance, among other human right abuses prevalent under the administration of President Muhammadu Buhari is an indication that all is not well with democratic practice in Nigeria (Emoruwa, 2019). The role of Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) in Nigeria's politics is instructive, especially as it serves a major force in advancing the rights of the people as well as demanding accountability of the government by probing its

actions/policies. The civil society organisation (SERAP), which specializes in promoting the socio-economic and political rights, is notable for challenging some of the policies and stance of the government which is antithetical to democratic practice. Instances include the litigation against the Federal government over the suspension of Twitter and the arbitrary use of the National Broadcasting Commission Act to sanction and harass independent television and radio stations in the country (Nwokoro, 2021).

Mukthar (2014) reviewed democratic rule and democratisation in Nigeria between 1999-2013, noting that the negative impacts of military rule in Nigeria will become a thing of the past through elite consensus aimed at economic and political development. This, according to the study, hinged on the position that the economic and political instability the country has witnessed over the years has made the people lose faith in the leadership of the country. The study revealed that democratic rule under the leadership of the People's Democratic Party (PDP), has since the return to civil rule in 1999 till 2013, increased the socioeconomic hardship of the people such that governance is only favourable to the political elites. The nature of leadership dispensed under the All Progressive Congress (APC) since 2015, evident in the autocratic stance, socio-economic challenges plaguing the country has proven that the ruling party under the leadership of President Muhammadu Buhari lacks idea in promoting good governance. The prevailing challenges that the people hoped would be addressed by the APC have been complicated due to numerous socioeconomic challenges characteristic of Nigeria's political space. Hence, the need for the birth of a new political party and candidates knowledgeable on the art of leading and capable of delivering good governance. Further, the study stated that the drive towards democratisation in Nigeria may be an impossible feat to achieve premised on the position that the tenets of democracy, especially the promotion and

respect for the rights of the people, judicial independence, and rule of law, are not being properly applied.

Similarly, Ojukwu, Mazi-Mbah, and Onwuekwe (2019:34) argue that while the practice of democracy in Nigeria may be taken to be suitable due to her population, economic and political dynamics, events and political happenings and the stance of the government suggest otherwise. The study notes that while elections are not free and fair in Nigeria, politicians, at their convenience switch from one party to the other with the objectives of satisfying their ambitions rather than promoting and protecting the interests of the populace and country, at large. The study concludes that the practice of democracy in Nigeria will continue to be at its nascent stage unless conscious efforts are made by the government, among other institutions of the state, to deepen its practice.

Momodu, Jude, and Gambo (2013) note that one of the major factors affecting democratic rule in Nigeria centres on intra-party conflicts. While the study acknowledged the invaluable roles of political parties in a democracy, especially in the areas of interest aggregation and articulation, the activities of political parties since the transition to civil rule have left bitter experiences in the country's political space. Party politics and the pettiness that surround their activities such as the emphasis on 'anointed candidates' perpetuated under the guise of internal democracy is another menacing factor that negatively impact party politics in Nigeria. The incidence of party switching and its attendant ramifications are some of the issues that intra-party politics brings to the fore.

The study reveals that corruption, which doubles as a characteristic feature of the country, is propelled by the political elites due to their inordinate ambition to take over the reins of government by all means. In this regard, political elites engage in incessant party defection without adhering to constitutional provisions. The study concludes that the absence of internal democracy and elite consensus is a drawback to democratic practice in the country.

Furthermore, while Shola (2009: 620) identifies the absence of defined political ideology among political parties in Nigeria as one of the core challenges negatively impacting democratic process and consolidation in Nigeria, Aleyomi (2012:12), avers that party defection and its ramifications are undeniably some of the key factors influencing politics and democratic practice in the country since 1999. The studies admit that the absence of internal democracy and the failure of political parties to advance the interest of the country and her people as their core mandate remain a clog in the country's quest towards democratisation.

The spate of corruption and corrupt practices perpetrated by public office holders in Nigeria, according to Aleyomi (2013), is a bane to democratic rule and practice in Nigeria. The study reveals that despite being the country with the largest economy in Africa with a large section of its population within the range of the labour force, institutionalizing democratic practice in the country proves to be a challenge. Relying on secondary data, the study reveals that corruption has become endemic among the leadership and its followers in the country. The study justifies that the act of corruption in the country is manifest in the misappropriation of funds by government officials, exchange of cash for votes, otherwise known as vote-buying, and sponsoring of thugs to disrupt elections. The study concludes that unless proactive solutions are adopted aimed to check the menace of corruption and corrupt practice, attaining socio-economic development, which is a core aspect of the democratisation process may be an impossible feat to achieve in Nigeria.

A study conducted by Omoleke and Olaiya (2015), which examined the democratisation process and good governance in Nigeria, states that since the Fourth Republic, the country has been caught in the web of bad policies which translates to bad governance. The implication, according to the study, reflects in the state of the country's declining economic and political growth. Furthermore, sharp practices orchestrated by politicians during elections have made the people lose confidence

in democratic practice in the country. Hence, while the people shun participating during elections, many resort to self-help as it pertains to fending for their socioeconomic needs due to the government's failure to meet the needs and demands of the people via good governance.

In the same vein, Tolu and Ogunro (2012) argue that democracy has the capacity to drive development given its emphasis on the roles of the people in the selection of credible representatives during elections. The study however notes that, as it concerns the Nigerian state, the adoption of democracy and its attendant principles such as election, has failed to act as a catalyst for economic and political development. The study argues that while the democratic practice is suitable for the country due to its dynamic political and cultural system, the pursuance of inordinate ambitions by the class of political elites; bad policy implementation; dependence on loans and aids among other challenges associated with the policies of the government have further pushed the country towards the path of economic degeneracy. The implications, according to the study, are evident in the spate of insecurity, youth unemployment, cybercrimes, armed robbery, and kidnapping, among other crises prevalent in the country. The study concludes that, in the case of Nigeria, democratic practice has failed to drive socio-economic development and democratisation process in the country. The above position speaks to elitism and its negative impact on Nigeria's politics. Although democratic practice is gradually being enshrined, ambitions and attitudes of some political elites aimed at advancing their personal interest over and above national interest continues to hinder the growth of democratic practice in the country.

2.2.3 Interest Groups and Democratic Practice in Nigeria

While the pursuit of the interest of their members is core, their roles in advancing democratic practices in a democratic state are invaluable. These groups, which function under the aegis of professional bodies, trade unions, and civil society organizations consciously or unconsciously

play the roles of articulating and aggregating the interest of the public with the objectives of institutionalizing good governance. Simon and Anne (2017) state that collaboration that often exists between political parties and interest groups plays a key role in promoting good governance in a democratic state. These roles are evident in the sensitisation process via the media or through seminars and workshops organized by these groups to help people express their approval or otherwise to the activities and policies of the government. Hence, these groups serve as a link between the people and the government. Through their workings and quest to drive the interest of their members, the groups act as checks and demand accountability of the government (Simon & Anne, 2017:1).

Similarly, Steven and John (2003) submit that as political parties seek to take over the reins of government, interest groups are particular about influencing government policies; political parties rely on these groups (interests/lobbyists) to achieve their objectives premised on using the machinery of the state to advance the demands and ambitions of these interest groups who engage in the mobilisation of the electorate during the electioneering process. The dynamics of these groups (lobbyists) lie in the position that they promote civic engagements, and as such improve political participation in a democracy (Steven & John, 2003).

Agbibo (2018) is of the opinion that the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) contributes its quota to the democratisation process in the country. These roles are most manifest in their show of support and aggregation of interest for its members and the group at large. Hence, their roles and activities arguably transcend activities and events that occur at motor parks and garages. Further, with reference to the politics and electioneering process in Southwest, Nigeria, the political parties endorsed by the NURTW most likely emerge winners. The government, on

the other hand, gives them all the needed support to help them thrive in their venture as a trade union (Agbibo, 2018:5).

In the views of Odoh (2020:1), the Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC) has since 1999 played a crucial role in promoting democratic practice in Nigeria. Such roles have seen the organisation support good government policies as well as protest against policies adopted by the government that are detrimental to the socio-economic wellbeing of Nigerians. For instance, the 'Occupy Nigeria' protest which took place between 2nd January 2012 through 14th of the same month, in response to the removal of subsidy on fuel by the administration of former President Goodluck Jonathan is a pointer to the roles civil society play at advancing accountability and good governance in Nigeria.

Nwodike (2017) notes that lobbying remains a widely practiced and controversial act given the complexities and secrecy often associated with it. It is noteworthy that former President Donald Trump on the 28th of January, 2017, signed an Executive Order, which called for a five-year ban on lobbyist groups in America's political space. Despite these actions, the roles of lobbyist groups in America's politics and influence on public office holders may not be tamed, in that, their roles have been institutionalised given their historical antecedents in the country's politics (Nwodike, 2017:4). In Nigeria, lobbying is fast becoming a tool for advocacy, especially in the legislative process. This, to an extent, promotes popular participation and by extension advance democratisation process (Nwodike, 2017).

Perticone (2019:1) argues that in United States politics, lobbyist groups are big financiers of political parties and candidates so as to influence the policies of the government. The study identified global brands like Facebook, the Internet and Television Association, the National Association of Broadcasters, Amazon, American Medical Association, Boeing, National Rifle

Association among the top lobbyist groups in US politics; contributing billions of Dollars for campaign and electioneering process. The role of the above organisations in promoting democratic process in the United States cannot be overemphasized. The same, arguably, may not be said of some notable news agencies and media outlets in Nigeria which rather than stand for the promotion of democratic values in the country engage in partisan politics. The mixed feelings among members of the public over the independence of TV Continental and Radio Continental with regards to its reportage is instructive.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The study considers state fragility theory, structural-functionalism, and patron-client theory. However, the study adopted structural functionalism and patron-client theories in explaining the subject.

State fragility theory noted that a state is categorised as weak or fragile if the instrumentality of the government and its agencies to protect its sovereignty is failing or has totally been lost to internal and/or external factors such as conflict among other socioeconomic and political challenges occasioned by bad governance (Tyagi, 2012). Hence, a fragile state will refer to the state that is incapable or has lost the political will to protect and provide for the needs of its citizens. Although the study examined the roles and importance of government in promoting good governance, it does not suffice in explaining the roles of interest group in the electoral process. This makes the theory insufficient in explaining the possible relationship between the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) and the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria. Structural-functionalism theory perceives the workings of the society as comprising of independent and dynamic parts that work in unison to advance its stability and viability. Though these constituent parts have defined or specified roles they perform, which varies from other parts,

these roles are interwoven with the ultimate objectives of driving sustainable growth and development of the society (Ritzer & Douglas, 2004). For a society to efficiently meet the needs and aspirations of the people, there should exist structures that perform specific functional roles; thereby promoting the workings of the governance in the state (Almond, 1966: 54).

In the views of Barnard (2000: 43), the structural-functionalism theory sees human society as consisting of independent but interrelated parts designed to meet the social needs of individuals and groups in such a society. Furthermore, he opined that just as the various organs of the body work together to keep it functional, so do the various parts of a society work collectively to keep the society operational (Barnard, 2000:44). The parts of the society are made up of different governmental institutions as well as beliefs and behaviours expressed by individuals or groups in society (Barnard, 2000: 44).

Similarly, the structural-functionalism theory explains how societies evolve and adapt to the changes recorded over a period of time. Society is a complex system of interrelated and interdependent parts that work together to maintain stability through shared values, languages, and symbols (Layton, 1997: 124).

Critics of structural-functionalism theory argued that the theory is teleological given that it does not embrace the cause-and-effect model. Rather, it examines societal issues with focus on what happens afterward (functions) and not before. Also, functional terminologies such as “interest articulation,” “aggregation,” “communication” and so on are regarded as loose and ambiguous (Dahrendorf, 1958; Meehan, 1958). Nevertheless, the theory is sufficient in examining the subject with regards to elections and the activities of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), in that while elections play a key function in determining the choice of representatives in a country, the NURTW functions primarily to oversee the transportation of persons from one

location or state to another. Although elections exist independent of the roles of the NURTW, the activities of the group are crucial to electoral practice in Nigeria. The group's role during the conduct of election cannot be overemphasized given their large following and influence at the grassroots level, made possible through the union's coordination of transportation services in the country. Hence, members of the NURTW cast their votes and galvanize support for the political parties, which to an extent increases the awareness and participation of the union's members in politics.

The patron-client theory otherwise referred to as 'clientelism' explains the nature of relationships that exist between political actors and groups in a society. This interaction exists in form of the exchange of goods and services for political support. Allen (2011) claimed that though the patron-client system may be argued to be best suited for, and predominant in a democratic state, its practice abounds in different societies of the world regardless of the system of government in practice in such state. This is premised on the fact that political actors seek loyalty and support from the people, and as such struggle to attain legitimacy either through negotiation or by compulsion; either way, a form of exchange takes place through socio-economic rewards in a liberal democratic state or via punishment like incarceration or deaths in autocratic regimes (Allen, 2011:31).

Howard (1984: 128) posited that the political system consists of two classes of people: those who wield political power and those who are of lower or humble background (Howard, 1984). The theory noted that all societies have a hierarchical relationship that exists between groups or classes of people: the political actors with influence, on the one hand, and the people, on the other hand. While the political actors depend on the people to help them attain their objectives of taking over

the reins of government during elections, the political actors, in exchange, reward the people economically or through other means, depending on the terms of agreement (Allen, 2011:11).

The patron-client theory was criticized for being too predictive and mechanistic in its stance on human behavior. Humans are dynamic and as such change over a period of time. While the theory is relevant to the subject, especially as it reflects the workings of politics as being practised in most countries of the world, not all persons that show support for a political party or political representative do it to attract any form of reward. For instance, the nationalistic stance of some African leaders like Nelson Mandela, Patrice Lumumba, Julius Nyerere, Kwame Nkrumah, among other notable nationalists in the fight against colonization and its attendant ramifications is instructive.

In the views of Stokes, Dunning, Nazereno, and Brusco (2013), the patron-client system is often manifest through vote-buying; voters' intimidation and harassment; the use of thugs and mercenaries to disrupt the electoral process; financial inducement of electoral officers, among other forms of electoral malpractices prevalent in sub-Saharan Africa. It is believed that patron-client practices are prevalent in developing countries with high unemployment rates, decaying socio-economic and infrastructural facilities, low political culture, and a high level of illiteracy (Allen, 2011). While some of the positions expressed by Allen are correct, the author's stance on Africa's political culture being poor is contestable. The reason is because the African continent, has, over the years, witnessed increased consciousness and participation of the people in the politics of their countries. This is with the objectives of promoting good governance on the continent.

The patron-client theory is relevant in understanding the nexus between the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), and the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria. While the

NURTW exists with the primary objective of protecting and promoting the interest of members, it tends to influence and realise these objectives in a transactional manner by supporting the government for reward. The influence that the leadership of the union command in the country is a pointer to the extent to which it arguably influences elections in the favour of its choice political party. It may be argued that the influence that the National and State leaders of the NURTW in the person of Alhaji Tajudeen Ibikunle Baruwa and Musiliu Ayinde Akinsanya otherwise referred to as MC Oluomo among others wield in Lagos is a testament to the different roles, they play in ensuring that the political parties and candidates they support win elective positions.

2.3.1 Theoretical Framework

Both theories (structural functionalism and client-patron) are apt for the study given that they are capable of explaining the role of the NURTW and their involvement in the electoral process in the country. Notably, the large following and influence the union wields gives credence to the structural-functionalism theory, which states that specific structure performs specific function for the development of the society. In the case of NURTW whose responsibility lies in the coordination of transport activities in the country, the group's services were employed by INEC in transporting election materials to polling units. It is noteworthy that INEC signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with road transport unions in conveying election officers and other logistics during the 2019 general election (Vanguard, 2018: 3). This gives credence to the role the transport union plays during elections in the country.

On the other hand, the patron-client theory underlines the influence of the NURTW in the conduct of its affairs. This may be traceable to the role they play in ensuring their choice candidate(s) and political parties emerge victorious during elections. Hence, the influence and other benefits the

union and its members enjoy in this regard come as a reward for the effort it puts into campaigning for its preferred political representatives and political parties.

In this context, patron could be referred to as “political actors” or “political office seekers,” while client could be referred to as “NURTW.” Against the backdrop of the fact that NURTW exists with the primary objectives of promoting and protecting the interest of their members, they tend to realize these objectives in a transactional manner by supporting the government for reward.

Given that the study examines the role of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria, structural-functionalism and patron-client theories inevitably aid in examining and understanding the underlying objectives of the study.

2.4 Gap in Literature

A number of studies have been conducted on elections, electoral system, and democratisation process in Nigeria. While some of these studies examined the impact of elections on Nigeria’s democracy and its quest towards democratic consolidation; others examined the challenges associated with the electoral process in Nigeria. Available evidence from studies conducted shows that elections and electioneering process in Nigeria and the quest to attaining democratisation are challenged by different factors, which stem largely from the quest to attain political power by persons seeking political offices by all means without regard for the will of the people (Adeniyi, 2006). Dele-Adedeji (2020) suggested that the credibility of elections largely determines the extent to which the country’s democratisation process may be attained, a core factor absent in Nigeria’s political space.

However, the opinions expressed in most of the studies reviewed show that although democratic practice in the country has endured since 1999, the system is challenged by different factors which

stem from the actions of political parties, government representatives, and interest groups. Studies also show that the roles of interest groups are relevant in deepening democratic practice. The roles of the civil society organisations and interest groups such as the Socio-economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP), National Rifle Association (NRA), National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), Nigerian Bar Association (NBA), among others, influence the workings of democratic practices in the countries where they operate.

While there exist several studies that have examined the role of democracy, elections and interest groups within and outside the context of Nigeria's political space, not many studies have examined the possible relationship that exists between the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), and electoral and democratisation processes in Southwest, Nigeria. This is because most studies often focus on the perceived nuisance the Union is characterized with, thereby neglecting the role they play during election. This is the gap the study identifies and seeks to fill.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discussed the research techniques adopted for this study as well as the procedures for data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The research was qualitative in nature. This was due to the nature of the study which focuses on human behaviour and their activities. Alasuutari (2010) avers that qualitative research methods allows a researcher the leverage to conduct a study in a natural environment by way of interacting physically with the respondents with a view to probing the variables under investigation.

3.2 Study Area

Though the study area was Southwest, Nigeria, the study focused on three states, namely, Lagos, Osun, and Ondo states. The study location was selected using convenience random sampling technique. Theodore (2009) noted that study areas and sample size may be selected 'conveniently' aimed at suiting the preference of the researcher and the study being undertaken. The cosmopolitan nature of the states, especially Lagos as well as the activeness of the union in the selected states, evident in the membership strength of the union, and the large number of vehicles engaged in public transportation services in the study areas were factors that influenced the selections. Agbiboa (2018) contends that the Lagos branch of the Union plays a key role in the emergence of any party candidate as Governor in the State. Each of the three selected states represents each of the three axis in Yorubaland/Southwest, Lagos/Ogun, Osun/Oyo, Ondo/Ekiti.

Lagos, though the smallest in terms of landmass; covering 3,577km² among the 36 states in Nigeria, is adjudged as one of the states in Nigeria with high concentration of commercial activities, which makes it the fifth-largest economy in Africa (Akinkuotu, 2015). The State boasts

of an estimated 17,552,940 population size (National Population Commission, 2017). Lagos State is replete with renowned tertiary institutions like the University of Lagos, Lagos State University, Yaba College of Education, Lagos Business School, and Lagos State College of Health Technology, among others (Akinkuotu, 2015). The All Progressives Congress is currently the ruling political party in the State with Babajide Sanwo-Olu as the Governor.

Osun State was created in 1991 from the old Oyo State; with a population of 3,423,535 in 2006 (National Population Commission, 2017). With a total of 30 local governments and three senatorial districts, Osun State is home to several famous landmarks like Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. Ile-Ife is another landmark in Osun State, which is often referred to by historians as a sacred town and the cradle of the Yoruba people (*My Guide*, 2020: 2). The All Progressives Congress is currently the ruling political party in the State with Gboyega Oyetola as the Governor.

Ondo State was created in 1976 and has a total number of 19 local government areas with an estimated population of 3,441,024 in 2006 (National Population Commission, 2017). Ondo State also houses important landmarks such as Adekunle Ajasin University, Akugba-Akoko, among other notable institutions (*My Guide*, 2020). The All Progressives Congress is currently the ruling political party in the State with Oluwarotimi Akeredolu as its Governor.

3.3 Study Population

The study examined the role of the NURTW in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria; thus, the study population was restricted to key informants who provided valuable information in order to achieve the objectives of the study. These included executives and members of the

National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), academics, officials of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), card-carrying members of the major political parties in Southwest, Nigeria, and electorates who doubled as commuters.

3.4 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The study adopted a purposive sampling technique for the selection of respondents based on their expertise on the variables being investigated. Also, the study adopted both primary and secondary sources of data. Primary data was collected qualitatively through the conduct of semi-structured interviews of 50 purposively selected Key Informant Respondents (KIRs) from the study areas. The breakdown is outlined as follows: NURTW: Osun State branch (7 respondents: 5 Members and 2 Executive members); NURTW: Ondo State branch (7 respondents: 5 Members and 2 Executive members); NURTW: Lagos State branch (7 respondents: 5 Members and 2 Executive members); Osun State INEC branch (5 respondents), Ondo State INEC branch (5 respondents); Lagos State INEC branch (5 respondents), academics from the Department of Transport from Nigerian Universities (3 respondents), 6 card carrying members of the All Progressives Congress (APC) and Peoples Democratic Party (PDP), two each from the selected study areas, 5 commuters/electorates. The respondents were selected given their experience and expertise on the subject.

Secondary data were sourced from books, journal articles, newspapers, seminars, conference papers as well as from the Internet. Data collected were analysed through thematic content analysis and descriptive methods.

Table 3.1 Presentation of Sample Size for Qualitative Data

S/N	Location of the Respondents	No. of the Respondents
1	National Union of Road Transport Workers, Osun State branch	7 Respondents
2	National Union of Road Transport Workers, Ondo State branch	7 Respondents
3	National Union of Road Transport Workers, Lagos State branch	7 Respondents
4	Independent National Electoral Commission, Osun State Branch	5 Respondents
5	Independent National Electoral Commission, Ondo State Branch	5 Respondents
6	Independent National Electoral Commission, Lagos State Branch	5 Respondents
7	Academics from the Department of Transport	3 Respondents
8	Card-carrying members of the All Progressives Congress (APC) and Peoples Democratic Party (PDP)	6 Respondents
9	Commuters plying public transport/electorates	5 respondents
		TOTAL = 50

Author's Compilation

3.5 Research Instruments

The research instrument for the study was an open-ended interview guide and focus group discussion. The instruments fostered discourse and interrogation of the key issues central to the research questions.

3.6 Validity/Reliability of Research Instruments

A number of measures were taken to ensure the reliability of the instrument that was used for the study. The research supervisor was consulted to ensure the research instrument was in line with the research objectives. Efforts were made to verify if the questions asked were relevant to the objectives of the research and that the wordings of the questions carried the exact meaning and

purpose of the research. While comments, suggestions and corrections were made, the responses of the respondents were effectively translated to avoid error of omission or commission. However, for ethical reasons, the confidentiality of the information supplied by the respondents was ensured and the recorded discussions were only presented for analytical purposes.

3.7 Data Collection

Data were collected using both the primary and secondary data collection methods. The primary data were sourced through an in-depth interview (IDI) of a purposively selected 50 respondents in the three states of Lagos, Osun, and Ondo. The secondary data were sourced from books, journal articles, newspapers, seminars, conference papers as well as from the Internet. Data collected were analysed through thematic content analysis and descriptive methods.

3.8 Data Analysis

The data obtained were subjected to qualitative analysis through the use of thematic content analysis and descriptive methods. Thematic content analysis refers to the process of making informed deductions and relevant inferences from the positions expressed by the respondents in order to achieve the stated objectives (Theodore, 2009). The analysis was situated within the specific context of the research questions as well as the assumptions of the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

History and Evolution of Interest Groups in Nigeria and their Impact on the Electioneering Process

Overview

This chapter focused on issues that surround interest groups and the electioneering process in Nigeria. The issue examined include; the evolution of interest groups and their activities on the electioneering process in Nigeria.

Historicizing Interest Groups and activities on the Electioneering Process in Nigeria

The interest group was a term interchangeably used with the term pressure group. The concept of pressure groups or interest groups implied an association of individuals, who come together voluntarily to defend a particular interest (Henry, 1972:468-488). Pressure groups are generally categorised into two: they are functional or promotional pressure groups and defensive pressure groups. The former refers to those pressure groups that not only focused on their selfish interest, but also sought to promote the interest of the general public. The likes of industrial or trade unions, human rights associations, and professional associations, all fall into this category. In corroborating this position, Abimbola (2002:41) averred that what was common to functional pressure groups was serving as the outlets for the social drives of their members. On the other hand, the defensive pressure groups were those groups primarily concerned with protecting the interest of their members as well as having a defined membership (Abimbola 2002).

Furthermore, Henry (1972:488-490) opined that pressure groups performed a relevant function, which majorly involved striking a balance between stability and change within a governmental system.

That being said, there are various pressure groups in existence in Nigeria, and they play varying roles in different capacities to cause social and national impact (Ayokunle, 2006:3-4). These groups have made immense contributions in the different areas of polity, in which they have operated. Corroborating this position, Abimbola (2002:39) expressed that functional pressure groups had contributed immensely to the democratic process in Nigeria, and at the same time, some interest groups might have contributed either covertly or overtly to the problem of democratisation in Nigeria. Nevertheless, Obasanjo and Mabogunje (1992:23) believed that interest groups were healthy tools necessary for the evolvement of a democratic culture.

Thus, without mincing words, the evolution and activities of interest groups or pressure groups in the electioneering processes in Nigeria could be historically traced to pre-independence. According to Abimbola (2002:40-41), attitudes and activities of interest groups on the electioneering process in Nigeria were visible before the attainment of political independence. In recent times, the activities of interest groups such as road transportation and marine workers' unions have become more crucial and visible than ever before as INEC signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the duo in order to facilitate successful logistics delivery for the 2023 general elections (*Premium Times*, 2022).

It is noteworthy that interest groups became more prominent when their interest shifted into political demands and not just the demand for wages. An example of this kind of event happened particularly in 1964, and its aftermath led to the formation of the Nigerian Labour Party that same year (Abimbola, 2002:42). The Nigerian Bar Association (NBA) also had an immense contribution to the democratic cum electioneering process in Nigeria. Thus, Abimbola (2002:42) averred that the NBA had been actively involved with upholding democratic principles in Nigeria and thus impacting the electioneering process of the country. Additionally, the NBA, aside from

being consistent with advocating the independence of the judiciary, was also committed to advocating the regard for the rule of law, as well as equality before the law. All these were indeed what constituted the bedrock of democracy (Abimbola, 2002). Thus, the activities of the NBA had not mainly been on protecting the interest of its members, but also the group had extended its function to promoting democratic values.

Functional pressure groups like the Human rights organisations had also significantly contributed to the maintenance of democratic values in Nigeria. Thus, it means that aside from having to organise lectures or symposia to sensitise and mobilise Nigerians on the maintenance of democracy in the country, these groups had gone further to confront the attempt of governments to either compromise democracy or stifle its progress (Abimbola, 2002:44). They had been able to do this by staging a series of mass protests and campaigns. An instance was the role the Campaign for Democracy (CD) played between July 5 and July 7, 1993. The CD called for mass protests to counter the annulment of June 12, 1993, presidential election (Abimbola, 2002: 44). Thus, Sola (1997:74-88) stated that the activities of CD and other pressure groups had an impact on the democratisation process of the country since their actions were what led to the unceremonious departure of General Ibrahim Babaginda from the power that same year.

Some pressure groups in Nigeria had equally contributed to the democratic process of the country, beyond their interests. Pressure groups like the Nigerian Medical Association (NMA), the National Association of Nigerian Students (NANS) fell into this category (Abimbola, 2002: 39). However, Abimbola (2002) further argued that some pressure groups had contributed either covertly or overtly to the problem of democratisation in Nigeria. This implied that while some pressure groups worked to promote democracy, some worked against its progress. Thus, talking about the impact of pressure groups on the electioneering process in Nigeria, historically, the

National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) had been a noticeable group whose activities were largely associated with the electioneering process in Nigeria (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007: 592). And as such, available literature also revealed that the activities of the NURTW in the electioneering process in Nigeria were “questionable”.

The NURTW is a trade association that comprises road transport workers in Nigeria. And according to Ayokunle and Akinpelu (2007:592), the NURTW was formed in 1978 as a successor to the Nigerian Road Transport Union that had been earlier formed in 1934. Since its formation, there has been series of NURTW activities that had taken place with political relevance (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:592).

The NURTW has been a typical representation of an organised group of transport workers, who are in a patronage relationship with big-men otherwise known as political actors in the democratic space (Ayokunle, 2006). Corroborating this position, Albert (2007:129-134) believes that there is a noticeable relationship between NURTW and politicians, and this dates back to the spiteful relationship that existed between the Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN), and the National Party of Nigeria (NPN) towards the preparation for a democratic transition in 1979, in Nigeria. He further states that at the early stage of this, the NURTW members became a part of the violent wings of these political parties.

Hence, there is a symbiotic relationship between NURTW and the politicians. This relationship, according to Albert (2007:130), has played a significant role in the electioneering and democratic process of Nigeria. This is evident in several local and state politics in Nigeria as well.

Thus, to be more explicit about the involvement and activities of the NURTW in politics and elections, Ayokunle and Akinpelu (2007:601), in their work, brought to the fore, the activities of the NURTW on electioneering process in two cities in the Southwest, precisely Ibadan and

Lagos, Nigeria. According to them, politician recruited and also partnered with the NURTW for a demonstration that would influence the electoral process of the region. For instance, the transport workers of the Lagos chapter in the late 1970s, with violence-instigated actions, worked for the success of the then governorship candidate of the UPN, Lateef Jakande. Moreover, some prominent political leaders in the early 1980s from UPN, representing Lagos and Ibadan conspired with the leaders of the NURTW in Lagos and Ibadan to gain the loyalty of these transport workers for the coming election (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:601-602). In addition, Albert (2007:128-133) opined that the involvement of the NURTW in the political arena in the early 1980s did change the political scene, thereby having a colossal effect on party politics and electoral violence in the two cities, Lagos and Ibadan. Their loyalty towards these prominent politicians resulted in these transport workers having to deploy thuggery and dangerous tools to intimidate the government, and to terrorise the electorate. In a nutshell, these violent activities on the electioneering process at that time was as a result of the impending 1983 General elections (Albert, 2007:128-133).

However, the activities of the foregoing pressure group (NURTW) were halted for a while or rather reduced as a result of the military government, which lasted for 15 years long, precisely January 1984 to May 29, 1999 (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007: 602). Notwithstanding, the present political dispensation in 1999 witnessed resurgence of the activities of this group in the electioneering process when other prominent politicians began to resurrect their interests in networking with the NURTW (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007: 602). Again, this became more notable particularly in Ibadan, as the leader of the NURTW during this period, Alhaji Latif Akinsola, also known as Tokyo, engaged in courting the patronage of politicians. Hence, with his involvement and his influence over other members of the NURTW, the Gubernatorial candidate

of the Alliance for Democracy (AD), Lamidi Adesina, was able to emerge as the elected Governor of the State (Animasahun 2013: 130-138). Thereafter, the leader of the NURTW, Tokyo remained a very important ally of Governor Lam Adesina (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:603).

According to Animasahun (2013:130-137), as the 2003 elections were drawing near, there were underground activities going on such as a move incited by the former NURTW leader, Tawa who was ousted by Tokyo. The move was to factionalise the NURTW, hence having two groups within a group supporting two different parties, AD and the PDP. The electioneering period witnessed acrimonious activities between political parties and NURTW, which later erupted into electoral violence. Not too long after the erupted violence, there were lots of issues such as the shift in loyalties as a result of the outcome of the election, and there was a power tussle yet again between Tawa, the former NURTW leader, and Tokyo, the then NURTW leader. This tussle led to a massive attack inflicted on Tawa since he would not succumb to being ousted by Tokyo from the chairmanship of the NURTW of the State (Animasahun 2013:134-136).

The marriage between the NURTW and the politicians got scarier as there were influences of the politicians on the NURTW as a tool for violent and intimidating activities. Thus, notably in December 2005, NURTW was deployed to invade the State House of Assembly and the seat of government at the State Secretariat, lots of havoc were caused. All these activities replayed themselves in the political scene again and again (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:604). Suffice to say that the activities of the NURTW on the electioneering process have mostly tilted towards electoral violence, intimidation, and so on.

The Nigeria electioneering process was usually characterised by electoral violence whereby several politicians deployed violence as a tool to either secure or retain power (Ayokunle, 2006:85-86). Meanwhile, the NURTW served as a resource pool where people with technical skills

in violence were being recruited for political reasons during elections (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:605). It was noteworthy that not all these Road Transport Workers were recruited to cause violence during elections. However, the fact was that the leadership of this group has control over a retinue of the thug-members of the organisation (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:441-442).

As earlier discussed, there were records of electoral violence witnessed in Ibadan mostly in 2003, 2007, and the 2011 electioneering processes (Ayokunle, 2006; Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007). Thus, the electoral process in the Southwestern part of Nigeria, and by extension, Nigeria unfolds a series of politickings such as a marriage formation between politicians and the transport unions breeding electoral violence and patronage politics. Since the politicians have the financial wherewithal, they strategically employed the service of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) to perpetrate violence and intimidate oppositions (Ayokunle & Akinpelu, 2007:442). Therefore, the activities of the NURTW were largely manifestation of the manipulations by the politicians (Ayokunle & Akinpelu 2007:608).

Suffice to say, therefore, was that the role of pressure groups in the electioneering process in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. However, while some contributed immensely to the electioneering and by extension, the democratic process of the country, some have caused more harm than good.

CHAPTER FIVE

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS

Introduction

This chapter presents, interprets and analyses data collected for the study during the fieldwork. Data for the study were collected through primary and secondary sources. While primary data were sourced via in-depth interview, secondary data were sourced via books, journal articles, online publications, newspaper editorials, published and unpublished dissertation and via the internet. A total of 50 purposively selected key informant respondents (KIRs) were interviewed for the study across the study areas (Ondo, Lagos, and Osun states). They include NURTW: Osun State branch (7 respondents: 5 Members and 2 Executives); NURTW: Ondo State branch (7 respondents: 5 Members and 2 Executives); NURTW: Lagos State branch (7 respondents: 5 Members and 2 Executives); Osun State INEC branch (5 respondents), Ondo State INEC branch (5 respondents); Lagos State INEC branch (5 respondents), 3 academics from the Department of Transportation from Nigerian Universities, 6 card carrying members of the All Progressives Congress and Peoples Democratic Party, two each from the selected study areas (Ondo, Lagos and Osun State), and 5 commuters/electorates.

It was noteworthy that the study examined National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) and the Electoral Process in Southwest, Nigeria (2015-2020) with the specific objectives of identifying ways in which the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) informally gets involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria; ascertain the implications of the activities of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) on the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria; investigate whether there is a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different State branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the electoral process;

and examine how the electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening democratic process in the country.

5.1 Data Presentation

The section presents the views and positions expressed by the respondents gathered through in-depth interview.

5.2 Ways in which the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) Informally gets Involved in the Electoral Process in Southwest, Nigeria.

In a bid to identify the ways in which the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) informally gets involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria, different scholars hold different views on the subject. For instance, Halpin (2015:56) noted that the conduct of elections across the world given its complexities, inarguably involved the roles and efforts of relevant stakeholders. These stakeholders included interest groups, the media, government and non-governmental agencies among other institutions, who played roles such as educating the electorates on the need to exercise their franchise, monitoring the conduct of elections to ensure it goes according to international best practices (promoting electoral credibility) (Halpin, 2015). Also, Avanish (2015) revealed that across the world, electoral management bodies (EMBs) often employed the efforts of support staff, who engaged in roles that would drive the success of elections in a country. In Nigeria, buildup to the 2019 general elections, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with different transport unions in the country. These unions include the NURTW, Road Transport Employers Association of Nigeria (RTEAN) and National Association of Road Transport Owners (NARTO). They were charged with the responsibility of conveying election materials to different polling units across the states of the federation (Ogunde, 2021).

While reacting to the research question, Respondent¹ affirmed the position expressed from the foregoing by declaring that:

Yes, being an NURTW member makes them no less an electorate, but then the level of participation differs. First as a Nigerian and then as an NURTW member they have the right to participate in election by voting or being voted for in as much as one is 18years and above. So, firstly, they participate directly as a voter and an electorate but beyond that they also play some roles which may not be captured under this niche. Over time, we have seen them trying to influence election for their own desired candidates. When we talk about informally getting involved in the electoral process, we need to have some parameters to measure their level of involvement, they also have some formal roles though not constitutionally stated but formally established by the memorandum of understanding (MoU) INEC signed in 2019 at the eve of the general election, which saddled the NURTW with responsibility of conveying election personnel and materials.

Respondent² who doubled as a staff of INEC opined that the electoral management body (EMB) worked cooperatively with transport unions in the country, and that NURTW was part of the MoU it signed with the different unions. According to him:

Yes, I am aware we (INEC) work with them (NURTW) during elections. We use their buses, drivers to convey materials from state office to various local government areas, and from these local areas to the several polling units. Also, we use them in reverse logistics after the completion of an election to carry the materials and poll officers back to their various Local Government Areas. Beyond the formal roles, they do not influence electoral process on the election day except occasionally, politicians do use them during campaigns and mobilise them. They do organise campaigns especially when they have a political candidate of their choice. So, to an extent they influence electoral processes informally. However, electoral outcomes are independent of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) input.

The above position was supported by Respondent³ who argued that NURTW participated in electoral processes. Hence, they collaborated with INEC as a commission during election by conveying adhoc staff to their various locations, from the ward level to the various polling units. According to Professor Okechukwu Ibeanu, INEC's Chairman, Electoral Operations and Logistics

Committee, the collaboration between the electoral management body and transport unions in Nigeria was core in promoting a hitch-free election in the country. Hence, members of the transport union assisted not only in conveying election materials on the day of elections but also conveyed INEC staff to different polling units in the state where elections were held (Ogunde, 2021). Respondent ⁴ noted that the only role NURTW played during election was to help in disrupting the elections, stating that they do not play any informal role during the conduct of elections in Nigeria. This position was supported by Respondent⁵. The positions of these respondents were summarized below:

No, I am not aware NURTW has an official role it plays during elections. I have seen it across literatures but as it concerns electoral management and all, I doubt INEC mentions them as a serious stakeholder in that regard. From experience having participated in several elections and as an INEC adhoc staff, correct me if I am wrong, the only role I think they play hinges on disrupting election on the election day. Most of them are ballot box snatchers, I have witnessed two cases in separate elections. Suffice to argue that they are engaged by politicians as thug who harass electorates.

One of the major challenges affecting elections in Nigeria was traceable to electoral violence. Bekeo (2010: 12) noted that electoral violence, which sometimes leads to the death and harassment of electorates were more often sponsored by persons and groups drawn from different sectors of the country, who were loyalists to either persons seeking public office or to political parties. Similarly, Arowolo and Aluko (2012) stated that the Nigerian political space had since the return to civil rule contended with the challenge of electoral violence, which were carried out in most cases by political thugs employed by political parties in the country.

Respondents^{6, 7} and ⁸ acknowledged that NURTW played both formal and informal roles during elections in the country. While the formal roles hinged on the MoU the transport union signed with INEC aimed at assisting in the conveyance of election materials and INEC staff to polling

units and collation centre, they were often employed by those seeking public offices and political parties during election campaigns and on the day of elections to canvass for votes. The respondents submitted that:

Yes, from time to time they (NURTW) participated, and they are always ready to involve in elections; they have formal roles the INEC has saddled them with, such as moving materials and personnel before, during and after election. INEC signed a Memorandum of Understanding with NURTW to assist in conveying election materials and adhoc staff to the different polling units in the country. INEC deals with the NURTW body generally, however, the nature of election in this part of the country or Nigeria in general is such that political actors do involve them in their electioneering campaigns (sic).

In the views of Respondent⁹ while identifying the ways NURTW participated in election, advanced that, ‘yes, they participated in electoral process first as members who go out to vote and then as a group, they are often times engaged by the electoral body INEC in conveying certain sensitive materials from a particular location to another. So, of course they perform important roles with INEC during election. Well, yes to some extent based on the politics of the country. NURTW is a union, which both formally and informally lobbies itself into political processes of the State and the country in general. The union often appears as a key or pivotal instrument in canvassing for votes for their principals (politicians). Also, because of the way this body was structured, the headship helped to lobby their people to probably favour a particular party member or to disrupt the electoral process. To justify this claim, when you look at Oyo, Tokyo was actively involved in late Governor Akala's administration because NURTW members were part of those that strongly supported Akala during election. In fact, some of their excos were appointed into some key government positions like Special Assistant (SA), aides, or key appointees of government functionaries.’

The above view was also supported by Respondent¹⁰ who remarked that- ‘the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) does not have statutory roles in the election process, they were only involved in logistics and distribution of electoral materials in Nigeria. Besides that they also played political roles as politicians utilise them to sabotage the logistics process. For instance, if a particular politician wants to get dominance over the others they can bribe or corrupt some NURTW leaders to give instructions to their members not to work efficiently as regards material distribution and this may affect the outcome of the election. For example, they might get to a particular polling unit late and this would affect the number of people that would vote during the time slated for voting. This was an inferred position that the NURTW members are informally used to sabotage electoral outcome.’ Wahab (2019) noted that although the NURTW has been coopted by INEC to play the role of a support unit to the electoral management body during the conduct of elections, the union in most account, especially in the Southwestern part of the country were renowned to show bias during election campaigns. These biases often emanated from their show of support to the ruling All Progressives Congress (APC). The case of Lagos state is instructive.

In the views of Respondent ¹¹ who doubles as personnel of NURTW, the union played an invaluable role before, during and after elections in the country by conveying electoral materials and INEC staff to polling units and back. Similarly, they were deployed by politicians given their large number to help in electoral campaigns. According to the respondent,

...of course, everyone participates in electoral process. The NURTW participates majorly in mobilisation/ transportation of electoral materials. Also, politicians engage us before, during and after elections, mainly because of our numbers. Our numerical strength enables us to play key role in many election processes.

The views of Respondents ^{12, 13, 14, 15, 16} and ¹⁷ affirmed that NURTW played a key role during elections in Nigeria particularly since 2015 at the instance of the MoU the union signed with INEC to assist in conveying sensitive and non-sensitive electoral materials and INEC staff to different polling units across states of the federation. Respondents ¹⁸ and ¹⁹ also exemplified the role of NURTW during elections in southwest, Nigeria as follows:

NURTW do participate in elections. This arrangement is based on the memorandum of understanding (MoU) INEC and NURTW signed vis-à-vis providing transportation services during the elections in the country by conveying both sensitive and non-sensitive materials to polling units during elections. You know we cannot move any of our men or material without them, for this reason we have to contact them some weeks before the election and they have to agree and sign a MoU with INEC for them to participate in the afore-mentioned roles. So, we pay them and they have to honour the agreement. We discovered that if they do not participate in the electoral process there will be no movement on that day. At times, some of them do disappoint, they were supposed to come on the eve of election, to come and carry men and materials to the RAC- to where the election will take place. But at times some of them will fail to come, it depends on the rapport between them and the politicians. Do you understand? But the agreement we had with them was that they should come and carry all our personnel and materials right from the state electoral office to the local government, then from the local government to the RAC (Registration Area Center). On the day of the election too, they were supposed to gather at the RAC to also help. Apart from the NURTW, other organizations like ACOMORAN also participate. They come to the RAC to also help in carrying the personnel and materials to the field. After the whole exercise, they will also bring them back as part of what we call retriever. We have to retrieve all the materials back to the RAC and back to the local government. INEC call this reverse logistics.

Odey (2008) noted that election management in Nigeria is a taxing venture. Aside from the cost involved in organising elections in the country, INEC was given the mandate to ensure that the votes of Nigerians count by entering into different agreements and adopting strategies that will promote electoral credibility. One of such strategies was traceable to ensuring a broad participation

in the electoral process. Despite the efforts put into achieving some of these objectives such as INEC's collaboration with different stakeholders and agencies in the country, elections were often marred by controversies owing largely to the involvement of persons suspected to be members of interest groups such as the NURTW in the country. In the views of Odunsi (2019), INEC in its bid to ensure the credibility of elections in the country, have over the years adopted different strategies. One of such strategies included the adoption of the smart card reader and the introduction of permanent voters' card (PVCs). The most recent strategy adopted by INEC in ensuring that elections were conducted without hitches hinged on the MoU the institution signed with transport unions in the country. This role required the NURTW to convey election materials and INEC staff to the Registration Area Center (RAC) and back to the collation centres. Respondent²⁰ while acknowledging the extent to which NURTW contributed to the success of the 2019 general elections by transporting electoral materials and INEC staff to the different polling units across the country maintained that INEC should envisage that some of the NURTW members may not understand the importance of elections or the nature of materials they have been saddled with the responsibility of transporting, hence, they should ensure that the best hands were picked through the inputs of top NURTW executives. The respondent advanced that:

They (INEC) do not use every member of NURTW because of the complexities of the materials they are charged with conveying. In our own law, members are free to support any candidate of their choice during elections, but the belief of most Nigerian is that members of NURTW are rascals and thug that grew up in street and so are bribed to cause violence in election. Whenever fight breaks out, people just believe that members of NURTW are responsible for it. But it is not always the case. It is important I mention here that the status of NURTW does not allow us (NURTW members) to openly support politicians, however, it is the will of our individual members to support politicians or to work for them.

Respondent²¹ holds a contrary view to the one expressed above; and as such argued that it would be difficult if not impossible to state that there is any law that prevented NURTW as an

organisation from supporting publicly political parties and their candidates. The reason was that even the leadership of NURTW had on many accounts showed public support to political parties. Take for instance, the All Progressives Congress (APC) in states like Lagos and Ondo. According to the respondent:

If I would be honest, their involvement is a little bit manipulative. Look at Lagos State for example, anytime there is an election, the NURTW chairman in Lagos Mc Oluomo is always actively involved. Even if there is no concrete proof, there are indications that he uses thugs and his members to intimidate and source for votes for his party (APC). Everyone knows, it is common knowledge that he does that. I would say that their involvement in elections in Southwest is that of intimidation. Okay, I think it was during the 2015 elections in Lagos. At an APC rally in Lagos, Mc Olumo was stabbed. I cannot really recall what transpired further. Normally the NURTW had no business with a political rally but they were there. They acted as 'security', so you can understand that if political party can use NURTW members (agberos) as security despite the bad records, it is easy to just use them as intimidating tools during elections.

Odunsi (2019) advanced that different controversies have trailed INEC's quest in using NURTW to convey electoral materials and INEC staff during elections, especially in Lagos State. For instance, the Lagos State Chairman of the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP), Dr Adegbola Dominic argued that the NURTW executives and its members publicly devoted support for the All Progressives Congress (APC) and by using their vehicles to convey election materials, the outcome of the electoral process may be compromised. In the same vein, Yujo (2019) argued that in states across the federation with a functional transport union like the NURTW, the members and executives of NURTW publicly galvanised support for the APC. Instances include Lagos, Osun, Ondo and Kwara States. The implication of the foregoing was that members of the transport union may use the MoU it signed with INEC as a means to promote electoral malpractices in support of the APC (Yujo, 2019).

The positions above raised concern over the credibility of electoral process in the country, particularly in states like Lagos and Ondo where the APC have over the years dominated the rein of politics. Respondent ²² who doubles as a member of the NURTW noted that the NURTW was one of the key stakeholders in Nigeria's political space first as electorates and secondly having entered into an agreement with INEC to engage in the transport of election materials and INEC staff to different polling units in the country. He argued that:

Yes, we participate in the electoral process because we are one of the stakeholders and we are electorates on the other hand. We actually participate in the electoral process. That is the view of the general public. They believe we play a violent role for politicians. Meanwhile, the behaviour of a person cannot be generalized on an entire body. While some of our members might be found wanting in uncalled-for behaviours during these elections, but in general we do not condole unruly behaviours. We just maintain peace and perform our duties.

Furthermore, the views expressed by Respondents ^{23, 24, 25, 26, 27 and 28} also affirmed the widely held views on the subject (research objective) that the NURTW through the MoU it signed with INEC allowed the transport union to enter into collaboration by assisting in the transportation of election materials and INEC staff to and from the polling units across the country aimed at ensuring that these (election) materials arrive the polling units on time so that the electorates can cast their votes on time and election results in each units can be collated and transferred to the central collating units for compilation and eventual announcement of the election winner. From the foregoing, it was deduced that one of the reasons for the collaborative efforts between INEC and transport union in Nigeria was aimed at ensuring that election materials arrived polling units on time. Despite this agreement, especially with the involvement of NURTW in the transportation of election materials, some elections in the country since 2019 had experienced delays. These delays, which emanated from the late arrival of election materials into the country to the failure of INEC to dispatch sensitive and non-sensitive materials to the different states on time for onward distribution were

some of the factors that impact on elections in Nigeria (Otoibhi, Abolade & Abe, 2022). Similarly, the breakdown in some cases of the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) technology as was witnessed during the 2021 gubernatorial election in Anambra state was another instance of the delays experienced during elections. This unarguably defeated the objective of INEC's collaborating with NURTW for quick transporting of electoral materials to the different polling units (Abolade & Abe, 2022). Nevertheless, it may be advanced that INEC was working assiduously towards ensuring transparent and credible electoral process. This led to the deployment of technology into elections such as the Smart Card Reader (SCR) and the Permanent Voters Card (PVCs) in 2015 and recently the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS), which enabled screening and fingerprints verification of the electorates.

Respondents ²⁸⁻⁴⁰ affirmed that the roles of NURTW during elections in Nigeria was aimed at assisting in the transport of election materials from the various INEC offices to polling units across the state of the federation with the objective of ensuring that election materials arrive the polling units on time. The above position was in concert with the views expressed by Respondents ⁴¹⁻⁴⁹ who also affirmed that NURTW's involvement in election in the country could be seen in the supportive roles they played in the distribution and return of sensitive and non-sensitive materials during elections. However, Respondent⁵⁰ opined that the NURTW exists basically as a transport union whose role was aimed at promoting the interests of their members; and as such, does not play any significant role during elections in the country. According to the Respondent, who doubles as a commuter and electorate in Lagos State:

The role NURTW, in my opinion, plays in the country as far as I know is to regulate the affairs of public transport services in the country. Also, they are renowned APC stalwarts. That is the only role I know they play in the country. Also, they have been

used according to media reports by politicians to cause havoc in the country during elections.

5.3 Implications of the Activities of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) on the Electoral Process in Southwest, Nigeria

This section explores the views expressed by scholars and the respondents on the implications of the activities of the NURTW on the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria. One of the core principles associated with democratic practice hinges on the position that it allows the electorates the right to select their preferred representative via an electoral process devoid of malpractices (that is, through a free, fair and credible election). Frey (2016) insists that representative democracy is one of the world's most practised political systems. This is traceable to some of the principles such as periodic electoral process, fundamental human rights, rule of law, among other tenets embedded in the system of government. Countries such as the United States and the United Kingdom, which have over the years allowed the practice of democracy to hold ground (democratic deepening) rarely contend with issues such as electoral malpractice (Frey, 2016). Meanwhile, countries with parochial political culture, especially those within sub-Saharan Africa still contend with several challenges such as electoral violence and election rigging. Hence, democratic practice in Nigeria with reference to the return to civil rule in 1999 has often been marred with several challenges. One of such challenges was associated with the country's electoral process that has been riddled with controversies such as electoral violence and malpractice carried out by persons seeking public office through the use of manipulative mechanisms (Kurfi, 2005). In the views of respondents⁵¹ on the implications of the activities of NURTW on electoral process in Nigeria, he argued that:

The implications of NURTW on electoral process in Nigeria are both positive and negative. NURTW helps INEC in transporting election materials from one polling unit to another; it has helped INEC conduct a hitch-free, and to an extent, credible election on the one hand. On the other hand, their

informal involvement has also affected the credibility of the election particularly in Southwest Nigeria, Lagos State, for example, in the past 16 years has been dominated by a single political party, the APC right from the time of AD in the fourth republic of 1999. The state has been dominated by just one political party, which many people believed has been made possible by the influence and support the political party derived from the NURTW members. Their stringent involvement in electoral processes has made Lagos State a one-party state, even in recent times, Jimi Agbaje and current contestants are trying to team up with the NURTW, in order to gain their support, come 2023 election and this may bring rancour between fractions of the NURTW during election.

Similarly, Respondent ⁵² who doubled as an INEC personnel observed that:

Beyond the formal roles, they (NURTW) do not influence electoral process on the election day except occasionally, politicians do use them during campaigns and mobilise them. They do organise campaigns, especially when they have a political candidate of their choice. So, to an extent they influence electoral processes informally. However, electoral outcomes are independent of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) input.

The above position was supported by Respondent⁵³ another INEC personnel who advanced that one of the ways by which NURTW impacted on electoral process in Nigeria was traceable to the delays emanating from the failure of NURTW staff to arrive the state INEC offices on time to convey election materials and staff on election day. The respondent revealed that:

When, for instance, they are meant to be available to transport materials and officials to a particular polling unit and they do not show up on time or boycott the process. It endangers or slow down the process of election. In remote areas, it hinders the smooth running of the election. As an INEC official, rating their impact on electoral processes in the region, we have not had serious issues leading to cancellation of election in the area. The National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) have been collaborating with INEC well and from time to time, INEC does sensitise them on what to do and the consequences of their actions.

Respondents ^{54 and 55} held a different view from the one expressed above. They argued that the role of NURTW at the instance of their rapport with the ruling All Progressive Congress (APC) have a negative impact on electoral process in the country. This was because most of the violence witnessed in the Southwest during campaign rallies and on the day of elections were reportedly caused by members of NURTW. Omobowale and Fayiga (2017) noted that the members of the NURTW in the Southwest have been alleged to be used as machinery to disrupt elections in the state by politicians. Members of the road transport were often used as political thugs to harass and intimidate electorates before, during and after elections. While many have died due to electoral violence, the outcomes of many elections in the Southwest have been compromised due to the actions and inactions of political thugs, who were suspected members of the NURTW in the Southwest (Omobowale & Fayiga, 2017).

In the views of Respondent ⁵⁶, the NURTW does not negatively affect electoral outcomes in the country due to the fact that INEC has a rule of engagement in its relationship with interests' groups such as the NURTW. The respondent observed that:

INEC have its rules of engagement in electoral processes and INEC follows these rules from line to line even if anyone wants to come in and does not follow the rules of engagement such person cannot fully be engaged. This means that NURTW cannot influence any of our electoral process except as a participant in the electoral process. Election outcomes have never been influenced by the NURTW. Before the NURTW was engaged in any electoral process, members signed a Memorandum of Understanding with clear-cut guidelines and responsibilities to INEC before, during, and after election. So far, they have been performing very well. When we engage them in services, there might be some out of scope in the process of carrying out their responsibilities, but INEC would call them to attention, and they would perform as expected.

Following the views expressed above, Respondents ⁵⁷⁻⁶² argued that rather than the NURTW having a positive impact on the electoral process in Nigeria they engage in activities that are

antithetical to electoral process and democracy in the country. This, according to the respondents, was due to the violent acts that some persons who doubled as NURTW staff perpetrated in support for APC in the Southwest. Meanwhile, Respondents⁶³ and ⁶⁴ who doubled as personnel of the NURTW stated that the transport union played key roles in the electoral process through the logistic services they offered the electoral management body (INEC). They stressed that NURTW members like other Nigerians (electorates) exercised their franchise, and so contributed their part towards electing their preferred representatives. Moshood (2009), while examining some of the core tenets of democracy, noted that one of the distinctive features of democracy was provision for popular participation. This implied that groups and individuals regardless of their social status and creed contributed their quota through their votes towards selecting their representatives who expectedly advance the interests of their constituency and the country at large.

The views of Respondents⁶⁵⁻⁷¹ reflected the widely held views expressed by the majority of the respondents vis-à-vis the positive and negative consequences of the activities of NURTW on the electoral process in Nigeria. Their views harped on the fact that NURTW through the logistics roles they played during election contributed towards ensuring the success of electoral process in the country. Similarly, some of the respondents advanced that members of the NURTW were often used by politicians to disrupt elections in the country particularly in Southwest, Nigeria. Respondent⁶⁸ particularly identified the economic situation of the Nigerian state as one of the major reasons responsible for some NURTW personnel involvement as political thugs to the politicians. According to the respondent:

Yes, the NURTW members are often used as tools to disrupt elections by politicians. Politicians influence them (NURTW) with money. This is easy because the money paid to the NURTW to participate in election is poor. You know INEC cannot deal with the group individually, we have to deal with

their leaders at their zones and units. So, when you deal with them in their zones, either the state level or local government level what happens is that their leaders actually use some parts of the money. They will not allow the money to go down to the drivers. If they allocate some amount of money for them, they bill INEC per vehicle. At times those money don't get to them, so by the time they discovered that the money their leader gave them is too small some of them will decide not to go to the field. Funds and politicians influence are also part of issues making the NURTW to sometimes disrupt elections.

The socioeconomic reality of the Nigerian state, it may be argued was one of the factors driving electoral malpractice in Nigeria. Oriowo (2018) opined that politicians in Nigeria took advantage of the economic situation of the country to wreak havoc during elections by engaging in exchange of votes for cash among other actions that negate credible elections. Also, Omobowale and Fayiga (2017) argued that one of the reasons responsible for the spate of electoral violence in Nigeria was traceable to the high level of poverty and youth unemployment in the country. Hence, politicians financially induced voters and political thugs with the objective of taking over the reins of government by all means (Omobowale and Fayiga, 2017).

Respondent⁷¹ claimed:

The obvious consequence of the NURTW activities in Southwest, Nigeria, is traceable to the fact that some of the elements within the union influence or tamper with election because they have been induced with money by politicians. The issue that borders on monetisation of politics and electoral process in Nigeria is a major concern for electoral credibility in the country.

The foregoing position was corroborated by Oghuvbu and Essien (2021), noting that the monetisation of election in Nigeria was a challenge that could not be divorced from the country's electoral process. Politicians induced interest groups and individuals to canvass for votes. Respondents⁷² and⁷³ contended that it was incorrect to identify only members of the NURTW as the persons who

were used by politicians to disrupt elections. This was based on the claim that not all members of the NURTW are unruly. According to Respondent⁷²:

... that is the view of the general public. They believe we (NURTW) play a violent role for a particular politician. Meanwhile, the behaviour of a person cannot be generalized on an entire body. While some of our members might be found wanting in an uncalled-for behaviour during an election, generally not all the members of the union exhibit unruly behaviours.

In the views of Respondent⁷³ on the implications of the activities of NURTW in electoral process in Nigeria, the respondent declared that:

I cannot say that NURTW activities impact negatively on election in Southwest. It will be incorrect to say that it is only NURTW members that are being used by politicians. Even the Nigerian Police, Nigerian Army and other parastatals are culpable. I am not equating them, but all elements and all active participators in the election can be used to influence the outcome of elections in the country. So, I can't say for sure that they use only NURTW staff; they use them just like they use every other government parastatal to rig elections. Even INEC is biased towards political parties that they want to work with.

The position expressed above was supported by Olaniyan and Amao (2015), who argued that the government use security personnel to harass and intimidate voters. In what they described as 'militarization of elections', they opined that there was barely any election in Nigeria even at the local government level that heavily armed security personnel were not deployed to provide security. These personnel, on the guise of providing security, were being used as tools to rig election in the country (Olaniyan & Amao, 2015).

Furthermore, Respondent⁷⁴ believed that NURTW activities negatively impact electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria. To the respondent:

O yes! It is a clear fact in Nigeria today, especially in the Southwest that NURTW members are usually mobilized to

intimidate electorates during an election. It is a huge fact, everybody knows that. The kind of business these people do, even the NURTW dealings with passengers and commuters, the way they intimidate the commuters, the way they forcefully twist people to extort money from them and the likes. In some instances, they harbour illegal weapons that they use against innocent masses. The politicians are much aware, and they try to employ them indirectly in electoral process.

Respondent⁷⁵ who doubled as a party executive of the APC corroborated the position expressed above by declaring that:

Firstly, one of those things that I see as the implication of the involvement of the NURTW members in the electoral process is a way of thwarting democratic processes. The way NURTW gets involved in electoral process, especially in an informal way sometimes serve as a means of thwarting people's will. Most of these people are hired by ambitious politicians, they are used to cause a lot of problem in some areas, thereby making people to feel uncomfortable to come out to vote. If these kinds of things happen in an electoral process, you will agree with me that the democratic process instead of being consolidated is being diminished at every point in time. The second implication that the NURTW has on the electoral process is that it takes away credibility, it takes away freedom, it takes away fairness in the electoral process. That means the election is not free, fair and credible for people to decide who will be their leader in an electoral process. These things are not too good for any democracy seeking sustenance and consolidation. I hope there will be an ethical rebirth and a reorientation on this particular issue, whereby most of the members of this body would be engaged ideologically; they will be engaged philosophically to see the reasons why there is need for change of attitude especially in the electoral processes.

The views expressed by other respondents⁷⁶⁻⁹⁹ which were made up of electorates/ commuters, personnel of NURTW and executives of political parties in the Southwest also corroborated the position expressed above. These respondents affirmed that the activities of NURTW have more

negative impact on the electoral process in Nigeria than positive impacts, manifesting in areas such as electoral violence, harassment of voters, ballot box snatching and stuffing, among other actions that negated a credible election were often traced to personnel of the NURTW. For instance, the studies conducted by The International Foundation for Electoral System (2020); Omobowale and Fayiga (2017); Transition Monitoring Group (2003); Olaniyan and Amao (2015); Oghuvbu and Essien (2021) among other related studies revealed that since 1999, which doubled as the period when the country returned to civil rule, electoral process in Nigeria had been marred by different controversies. These controversies, according to the study, ranged from electoral violence, exchange of vote for cash, ballot box snatching and intimidation of voters. The implications of the foregoing hinged on the fact that votes do not truly count. According to the International Foundation for Electoral System (2020), the quest to access political office remained the major driver of electoral malpractice in the country. Hence, politicians and their political parties used cash to influence the electoral process by deploying interest groups and individuals to engage in violent actions capable of disrupting the electoral process.

Omobowale and Fayiga (2017) identified some members of the NURTW as part of the interest groups in the country often used by persons seeking public office to pervert the outcome of elections. The positions expressed in literature corroborated the majority of the views expressed by the respondents. This admittedly questioned INEC position in adopting the NURTW as part of the transport union in the country to provide logistics support to the Commission during the conduct of elections. Thus, without realising it, INEC in a bid to advance efficiency in the electoral process may be further compounding the challenges affecting electoral process in the country.

5.4 Uniformity of Perspective and Approach among the Different State Branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the Electoral Process

In a bid to investigate whether or otherwise there was uniformity of perspective and approach among the different state branches of the NURTW in relation to their involvement in the electoral process in Nigeria, the views of academics from the Department of Transportation, INEC personnel as well as those of NURTW personnel from the study location, Lagos, Osun and Ondo states were sought. This was supported with relevant literature. Nyamnjoh (2017) suggested that one of the core perspectives that differentiated pressure/ interest groups from other groups in the society hinged on the position that they chart a common course towards achieving the goals and objectives of their members using all forms of instruments/ techniques such as demonstration, picketing, negotiations, strike actions, among others. These forms of techniques gave credence to the position that there was uniformity of perspective adopted by interest/pressure groups.

While responding to the research objective on the uniformity of perspectives among members of the NURTW in relation to their involvement in politics in Southwest, Nigeria, Respondent¹⁰⁰ opined that the uniformity that exists within the NURTW hinges on the fact that members of the transport union across states in the Southwest wear the same uniform (green and white). However, in relation to their involvement in politics, uniformity does not exist given the fact that the different state branches of the union may have different persons they are supporting or endorsing during election. In the respondent's view:

... you talk of the patterns of involvement, naturally based on their structure, they wear the same uniform (white on green). Each state branch has their own preferred electoral candidate for instance, while NURTW in Ondo may want a PDP candidate, the other in Osun might want an APC candidate; there is always conflict of interest with respect to the choice of candidates. In politics, there are no permanent friends or enemies, there is only permanent interest. Based on that template, there is no uniformity in the pattern and approach among the different state branches of the NURTW with respect to electoral processes.

Respondent¹⁰¹ who doubled as an INEC personnel stated that there was uniformity of perspective as it concerns INEC engagement of the transport union during elections. This uniformity, according to the respondent, was possible because INEC reached out to the national body of the transport union (NURTW), who in-turn communicated the decisions to the state transport unions. In the words of the respondent, ‘yes, there is uniformity. Let me take for instance when election is coming, the National headquarters of INEC would engage the leaders of the NURTW at the national level, then the headquarters (INEC) would inform the state level to engage the state leaders of NURTW. So, there is uniform rules of engagement right from the national level down to the state level and this cuts across all states in Nigeria’. The foregoing position was supported by Respondent¹⁰² who noted that there was uniformity vis-à-vis NURTW involvement in politics. This was because NURTW were only third-party logistic personnel, and their uniformity was informed by the timeframe given to them by INEC regarding transport services during elections. The position expressed by Respondent¹⁰³, who is a member of the NURTW reflected a non-uniformity in perspective among the different state branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in politics. This, according to the respondent, was based on the position that the different state branches of the NURTW have different candidates they endorsed during elections.

Hence:

Our perspectives can never be uniform; we all do not reason the same way. It is virtually impossible to have people of same opinions and perspective though they work together. Different states or branch chairmen might have a different opinion on the candidates. We have seen cases of refusal to work for candidate they do not endorse. However, our primary duty is to the garage and not for election; our role at election is secondary just to give us legitimacy. One way or the other, the government controls us, that is why we support any candidate we feel would likely emerge.

Gatt and Owen (2018) remarked that although the goals and objectives of interest groups may be the same in relation to pursuing the interest of their members, the approach adopted in achieving these goals may differ. While some members of such groups may be radical in their approach towards pressing home their demands, others may be liberal. These forms of divergence undeniably led to conflicts among members of interest groups. The foregoing underscored why there were often cases of clashes between members of NURTW within a state. These conflicts often surfaced due to differences in opinions expressed by members of the union within a state over matters that concern perhaps the interest of the members, loyalty to different heads of the union or candidate to support during elections. For instance, Evenlyn (2022) submits that on many occasions there have been reports of violent clashes between factions of the NURTW in different states in the Southwest. These clashes have not only resulted in the deaths of commuters as well as members of the NURTW, but it has also disrupted economic activities whenever such incidences occurred.

According to Moncada (2016), interest groups served as a channel between the government and the people by way of demanding good governance, contributing their quota towards conscientising the people on the importance of exercising franchise as well as providing supports to candidates and political parties of their choice during elections. In the United States, for instance, some interest groups were renowned for forming political action committees (PACs), and subsequently raised funds for their choice candidates that would promote their interests when elected to offices.

To Respondents^{104, 105 and 106} there was no uniformity of perspectives between the state branches of the NURTW in the Southwest. This was because there exist different factions within the transport union, who supported different political parties that would promote their interests. Hence,

differences in views and perspectives made it impossible for the existence of uniformity in their involvement in elections. In the views of Novoa (2015), one of the challenges that affected the functionality of interest groups was lack of unity or disorganisation among the members of such groups. This was due largely to the differences in ideology. However, the views expressed by Respondent¹⁰⁷ differed from the above positions, which was premised on the position that the NURTW during elections held meetings with heads of the different branches in the Southwest aimed at deciding the candidate to support during elections. Hence, the respondent argued that:

Yes. There is a uniformity of perspectives among the NURTW in the Southwest because we have regular meetings before elections are conducted. When it comes to election period, we sensitize our members, we talk to them about the role we have to play. What an NURTW member is doing in Lagos State is what an NURTW member in Ogun State and Osun state will be doing at the same time, that is to maintain peace and tranquility, trying to help the process, voting for candidate of their choice.

The above position was supported by Respondent¹⁰⁸ who stated:

...I think to some extent, in Southwest there is this cooperation. Like we have seen overtime, in some case where elections are to be held in isolation maybe a rerun election or a by-election. You will see NURTW member being mobilized from neighbouring states of the Southwest to participate. So, there is this coalition among them in the Southwest. This uniformity does not extend to the national level but within the regional level particularly the Southwest. In my opinion, I will say that there is a strong cooperation within this people. Even though they have differences, but they are very much in solidarity with themselves when it comes to electoral matters.

Similarly, Respondent¹⁰⁹ averred that:

NURTW in Osun, in Ondo, in Oyo and in every other state in the Southwest; if you look at their system keenly you will see that one thing is common or one thing is paramount in the union

and that is strong leadership. What I mean by strong leadership is that whenever the members of the union get a direct order from the national body to pursue a particular course, they often work in unison towards achieving their set goals and objectives.

Respondent¹¹⁰ however held a contrary view to the one expressed above. Towing the perspective of the views expressed by some of the respondents on the non-existence of uniformity of perspectives among the different state branches of the NURTW, the respondent advanced that:

Like I said, the way they do in Lagos is totally different from the way they are doing it in other states. Don't forget that in each state the governor also influences who heads the NURTW. For example, in Oyo state you will see how the governor is actively participating in the procedures of the NURTW members in garages all over Oyo state. You know that APC is not in Oyo, you can see that uniformity if there is no opposition. If there is a kind of constitution or strong law that is holding the NURTW at the centre, I think things can be done. I believe that they are being used according to how it is done in their state.

Respondent¹¹¹ views corroborated the one expressed above, and as such stated that 'it will be impossible to achieve a uniformity of perspective by the state branches of the NURTW in relation to the union's involvement in politics. This was based on the position that the state branches have different leaders with different leadership tactics they adopted in their states whether during an election or otherwise. This explained why conflicts surfaced from the different factions and divisions between members of the state branches of the union'.

The majority of the views expressed by the respondents revealed that one of the major drawbacks influencing the workings of interest groups revolved around areas of conflicting interests. Although interest groups were primarily established to advance the common interests of their members, the differences in ideology and thought processes made it difficult to avoid areas of conflict. Consequently, Bayero (2016) argued that it was nearly impossible for interest groups to chart a

common course without areas of conflict. These areas of conflict surfaced due to differences in ideology, the quest to show superiority of thoughts or plans or lack of organisation within the leadership structure of such group. The same applies to the NURTW; according to Aliyu (2022), who advanced that the leadership structure of the NURTW often provided room for tension and area of conflict. A case in point was the discord that recently occurred between Alhaji Musiliu Akinsanya popularly known as MC Oluomo, and the national leadership of the union led by Alhaji Tajudeen Baruwa. The consequence of the foregoing impasse was the brewing division between the members of the different branches of the union in different states in the Southwest, leading to the temporary suspension of the operations of the union by the Lagos state. These issues undeniably brought about variance in perspectives vis-à-vis the union's role in electoral process in the country.

5.4 How the Electoral Process in Nigeria may be Enhanced to Improve Voters' Confidence Thereby Deepening the Democratic Process in the Country

The fourth research objective adopted for the study ascertained how electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening democratic process in the country. Democratic practice in Nigeria has since the 1960s been grappled with different controversies, which led the military to intervene in the country's political space. Some of the notable crises that had characterised the country's democratic practice/ political space included: the Kano riot of 1952, Action Group (AG) crisis of 1962, census crises of 1962/1963, general election crisis of 1964, Western Nigeria election crisis of 1965, general election crisis of 1979, among others. These crises were admittedly borne out of ethnic and ideological differences that existed between politicians in the country. Odo (2015) remarked that democratic practice in Nigeria was one that had been marred with different challenges since the 1960s. At the core of these challenges were the issues traceable to the misuse of power, disregard for the rights of the citizens, misappropriation of public funds by members of the political class, among other actions that were

antithetical to the workings of democratic practice. In the views of Ukase (2014), the factor negatively impacting on the electoral process in Nigeria was borne out of poor leadership and by extension, bad governance. This underscored the far from impressive level of development witnessed in the country since the return to civil rule. Hence, if the political elites and those at the helm of affairs will chart an intentional course by advancing good governance vis-à-vis ensuring the workability of democratic practice in the country, it will serve as a channel through which the Nigerian state will attain sustainable development.

While suggesting ways by which electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence, and so deepen democratic practice in the country, Respondent¹¹² developed a tripartite solution. Accordingly,

A number of things can be done to increase voter's confidence as well as deepen Nigerians quest for credible election. Some of these include but are not limited to the use of technology, we need to go beyond paper-based elections, aside from the fact that electronic election guarantees the credibility, freeness and fairness of election it also saves cost. Also, electronic transmission of results will reduce manipulation and distortion of election results to the barest minimum. The President's assent to the electoral bill is a welcome development as it will go a long way in facilitating the much-needed reforms. There should be total isolation of NURTW from electoral process; when INEC is well funded and is headed by futuristic individuals, they would be able to organise elections without the interference of the NURTW members formally or informally. If they are reduced to electorate, who only come to vote during the election then there won't be possibility of these people influencing the election outcome. Thirdly, the security of polling units should be strengthened so that voters would be confident to come out on election day to cast their vote. Most electorates are politically apathetic not because they want to but for the fear of being killed or injured on election day. If the electoral atmosphere is secured and well protected, voters would deem it fit to come out and cast their votes.

In the views of Respondent¹¹³, ensuring transparency at the polls was one of the ways that voters' confidence may be improved and so deepen democratic practice in Nigeria. Hence,

Transparency, in my opinion is the solution to Nigeria's electoral process. Before now, many do not go out to vote because they feel results are just announced but with the introduction of Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) people now believe that if you have your voter's card there is no way someone is going to vote for you. This new innovation captures your facials and your thumbprints, results would be announced instantly at the polling units as opposed to the past when ballot boxes were taken to a different location before votes were counted and results announced. Each political party agent knows the number for each polling unit; therefore, people are encouraged to have their voter's card so as to make their votes count. It was used during the Anambra elections and recorded success.

The Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) was introduced by INEC on September 11, 2021, during the Isoko-South I State Constituency Bye-election in Delta State to replace Smart Card Readers (SRCs), which was first introduced during the 2015 general elections. The BVAS was reported to have unique features that will check the challenge of double voting and identity theft at the instance when one person uses another's permanent voters' card (PVC) (Odorie, 2022). Some of the features of the BVAS included dual capacity for fingerprint and facial authentication of voters (Odorie, 2022). The BVAS, which was used during the gubernatorial elections in Anambra state was marred by several challenges, particularly technical glitches during the elections, as such slowed down the voting process (Ojochogu, 2022).

The positions expressed by Respondent^{114 and 115} showed that there was a need to re-conscientise Nigerians on the importance of exercising their franchise. This, according to them, would be achieved if the operations of INEC were organised such that transparency at the polls were guaranteed as this will check the challenge associated with voters' apathy, which was one of the

factors impacting on electoral process in the country due to the prevalence of electoral malpractices such as ballot box snatching among others. Their views were summarised below:

The issue relating to ballot box snatching, which is one of the major challenges affecting our democracy with reference to 1999 has made election far from credible. We have witnessed rigging at various levels both federal and state levels. No democratic system thrives on electoral malpractice, so it is important we first and foremost check electoral malpractice during election. There is the need for formal and non-formal agencies at the institution of the state to re-conscientize Nigerians on the need to vote on election day as many Nigerian voters are dissatisfied with our electoral process. People prefer monitoring the election outcome online to coming out to vote due to fear of being attacked. We need to jettison all forms of political apathy and participate actively in election and not just that, but also monitor the outcome of these elections to ensure our votes count. There is no polling booth on social media, it is sad that supposed intelligentsia sit at home and follow the media for updates on elections. The introduction of smart card readers though it has its challenges, if further developed can build to an extent the confidence the electorates have in the electoral process. It is capable of deepening democratic practice in Nigeria.

Respondent ¹¹⁶ identified the solutions to electoral challenges in Nigeria to include the ‘introduction of blockchain voting by INEC, which would ensure that voting can never be manipulated. This is because if a block is manipulated, it shows on the other block. Also, INEC needs to make registration process easier such as via one’s mobile device as this will increase the number of electorates that will exercise their franchise.’ While Respondent¹¹⁷ recommended the introduction of independent candidacy into the Electoral Act, Respondent¹¹⁸ noted that electronic voting should be enhanced such that it prevents all forms of electoral malpractices as this will enhance voters’ confidence and contribute to deepening democratic practice in the country. While examining the importance of electronic voting, Matic (2019) advanced that digital technology is making all frontiers of human endeavours easy. Hence, the use of electronic voting was

advantageous because aside from checking the challenge of electoral malpractice, it serves as a conduit through which election results may be monitored as votes are cast and collated. This was one of the means that would help improve electoral process in developing countries of the world.

Also, Respondent ¹¹⁹ advanced that:

We should restructure the electoral process. People who are leaders or aspiring for position should look at the authority given to them eventually as a mandate to serve not as a means of aggrandizement or enriching oneself (stacking money in the house); if they pick up the mandate as that of service at the end of the day people would remember them for the legacies they left behind. Taking Jakande as an example, he didn't amass so much but look amongst those who are struggling for power today, they go as far as 'breaking the bank' only to focus on recovering their spent resources when they get into office.

Further, Respondent¹²⁰ opined that:

The first stage of enhancing our electoral process is by making some amendments to some of our electoral acts. There is a need to modernize the ways we conduct elections by taking clues from developed countries. This will bring enhancement and more public confidence in our electoral process. As you know, the recent approval by President Buhari to the Electoral Amendment bill will do a lot in this regard. This is one of the ways INEC is trying to improve our electoral process.

Similarly, Respondent¹²¹ averred that:

One of the ways to improve voters' confidence is through sensitization of the electorates. There is a need for the INEC, NURTW, among other civil society organisations to re-orientate the public that free, fair and credible election will be guaranteed in Southwest states and Nigeria as a whole. If there is confidence from the electorate regarding the NURTW that they would not be intimidated when they go to vote, it would help enhance the electoral process.

It should be noted that the views expressed by Respondents¹²²⁻¹³⁰ were similar to the ones expressed above. The views of the respondents ranged from the amendment of the electoral act

such that it gives room for the digitalisation of the electoral process to recognising independent candidacy. Also, some of the respondents advanced that transparency in the electoral process must be made the mantra of INEC such that the votes cast by the electorates count and are not manipulated by either INEC officials or politicians. Parts of the positions also expressed included ensuring that adequate security is provided on the day of election such that the security of the electorates is guaranteed as well as curbing any potential incidence of ballot box snatching, stuffing, violence and intimidation of voters. Odo (2015) advanced that lack of transparency was one of the factors negatively impacting on electoral process in Nigeria, particularly since the return to civil rule in 1999. This position was supported by Edward Kallon, the United Nations Resident Coordinator in Nigeria, who argued that the solutions to the challenges plaguing electoral process in Nigeria was traceable to the absence of credible and transparent elections. He further stated that the quest to deepening democratic practice in the country lies largely on unifying force between the government and political elites, on the one hand and INEC on the other hand (Igbohor, 2019). Respondent¹²⁶ gave a robust analysis on how voters' confidence may be improved vis-à-vis electoral process in Nigeria as follows:

There are many ways by which voters' confidence may be improved in Nigeria. Firstly, there is a need for electoral reform that will jettison sentiment, bias on the part of political leaders and on the part of the electoral umpire. Also, if we are to improve the electoral system in Nigeria in a way that will boost the confidence of the people, then there is a need for a broad-based orientation across levels whereby everybody will be given adequate awareness about what is obtainable in any electoral process. For instance, what people need to know about the electoral process. Another thing that is important is that the political office holders should have the political will of appointing people of high pedigree into the electoral commission. In such a way that people that will be appointed will not have any form of political affiliation. They must be

able to come up with people of impeccable records, people of strong antecedents, especially people that have contributed highly to the development of our democracy, to form part of the people that will pilot the affairs of the electoral commission. If all these are done, I believe we are going to have a lot of improvement in our electoral system in Nigeria.

The discourse on the amendment of the Electoral Act has long been at the fore front of Nigeria's political space. This was due to the series of discrepancies that have characterised electoral process in the country since the return to civil rule (Itodo, 2019). The Koffi Anan Foundation (2019) stated that studies conducted by organisations and institutes like the European Union and the joint report of the National Democratic Institute (NDI) and the National Republican Institute (NRI) revealed that many Nigerians were dissatisfied with the electoral process in the country. One of the solutions proposed, therefore, was the amendment of the Electoral Act that will promote transparency and inclusive participation in the electoral process. The Electoral Act (Amendment) Bill 2022, which has provisions such as electronic voting and transmission of election results, timelines for campaigns and candidate nomination, review of election results declared under duress, among other provisions, has been signed into law by President Muhammadu Buhari on the 25th of February 2022 despite the President initial withdrawal of assent (Cyril, 2022). Many Nigerians have since remarked that the signing of the 2022 Electoral Act (Amendment) Bill into law will deepen democratic practice in Nigeria, and so, serve as check to the many challenges confronting the electoral process in the country.

In the views of Respondents^{131,132 and133}, one of the ways to enhance voters' confidence and deepen democratic practice in Nigeria hinged on the proactive role that INEC must play by ensuring that technology such as the BVAS works effectively and efficiently. This will eliminate delays experienced at the polling units as well as check the incidence of double voting. INEC, according

to the respondents, should adopt effective measures that will make voters registration easier for eligible electorates such as using one's mobile device. In the words of Respondent ¹³³, 'one of the factors dissuading some Nigerians from participating in elections was traceable to the difficulties involved in the voters' registration exercise. It will interest you to note that many Nigerians have been disenfranchised due to the stress and delays involved in the voters' registration exercise. If the process is digitalised such that people can get registered via their mobile phones and pick up their permanent voters' card (PVCs) at will, it will increase the number of persons eligible to vote.'

5.6 Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the findings of the study. Findings on the first objective of the study, which identified ways by which the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) informally gets involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria, revealed that NURTW largely gets involved by providing logistics for the transportation of election materials to different polling units aimed at ensuring that electorates exercised their franchise without delay on election day. This corroborates the views of the majority of the respondents interviewed. It should be recalled that INEC in 2015 signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with NURTW, and expanded it to involve other transportation unions in the country to include Road Transport Employees Association of Nigeria (RTEAN) and National Association of Road Transport Owners (NARTO) in 2019 (Adeyeye, 2018). In the words of the INEC Chairman in 2019 on the importance of expanding the MoU on the transport of election materials to include other notable transport unions, he argued that 'to ensure that INEC staff and election materials leave the state offices to the 774 Local Government Areas (LGAs) in the country, 8,809 electoral wards and 119,973 polling units, the Commission requires over 100,000 vehicles. Hence, it was necessary to partner with transport unions in the country so as to achieve the goals of ensuring that elections

were conducted early enough so that all the electorates will have the opportunity to exercise their franchise' (Adeyeye, 2018). The foregoing captured structural-functional theory, which stated that across societies different structures exist and perform specific functions towards contributing to the growth and development of such society. In the event of a failure of a structure to perform its assigned functions, it may bring about a drawback thereby impacting negatively on the society. INEC at this instance performed specific function, which hinged on the conduct of a credible election in the country. Hence, working in concert with the NURTW whose function has to do with conveying election materials and INEC staff to the different polling units in the country will further enhance electoral process in Nigeria, and ensure that the electorates exercise their franchise on time and at their designated polling units.

Mackintosh (2019) justified the MoU signed between INEC and other key stakeholder agencies in the country such as the NURTW and the Federal Road Safety Corp (FRSC) in 2019 aimed at ensuring that elections in the country were conducted without hitches. While NURTW will ensure that INEC staff and materials arrive polling units on time, the FRSC will ensure the safety of commuters among other road users on the day of elections This gives credence to the structural-functionalism theory adopted as part of the framework of analysis for the study. The study also reveals that different controversies have trailed INEC's involvement of the NURTW in the provision of logistics, which noted that most of the members of the NURTW were political stalwarts of the All-Progressives Congress (APC) due to their public show of support. Hence, the involvement of the transport union during elections has the tendency to jeopardise the outcome of the electoral process (Odunsi, 2019). For instance, the Lagos State Chairman of the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP), Dr Adegbola Dominic argued that at the instance of the public support NURTW executives and their members have shown to the APC that using their vehicles to convey

election materials may compromise the outcome of the election (Odunsi, 2019). The position expressed herein calls for urgent attention by INEC vis-à-vis ensuring the close monitoring of elections in the state.

However, the study also finds that the status of the NURTW prevents the union as an interest group from the public show of supports to political parties and politicians. Hence, members of the transport union are expected to be politically neutral but can individually support and be members of political parties. This position is flawed on the ground that the leadership of the NURTW, particularly in Lagos state and other Southwestern states have on many accounts publicly endorsed political parties. Consequently, the study reveals that on many occasions before, during and after elections members of the NURTW have been involved directly or indirectly in violence such as harassment and intimidation of electorates and members of the opposition parties, ballot box snatching and stuffing among other acts antithetical to electoral process. Akoni (2022) notes that the persistent clashes between NURTW and other interest groups in the country, which often leads to the death and destruction of property in the Southwest questions the credibility of the MoU INEC and the transport union signed for the promotion of effective electoral process.

However, the study also finds that some Nigerians are not aware that INEC signed a MoU with transport unions in Nigeria to act as a support system in providing logistics during the conduct of elections in the country. This perhaps gives credence to the prevailing political apathy in the country, which may be argued emanated from the discontent some electorates have over the conduct of elections in the country. According to the Transition Monitoring Group (2003), many Nigerians failed to participate in elections due to the dissatisfaction they have over the electoral process. The perception that their votes may not count was one of the factors driving political apathy in the country, particularly among the youths.

Findings on objective two, which ascertains the implications of the activities of the NURTW on electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria, reveals that the involvement of the transport union in providing logistics support during election by transporting election materials and staff to the different polling units before and after elections contributes towards achieving a hitch-free electoral process. However, some of the views expressed by the respondents particularly INEC staff reveal that despite involving the NURTW in transporting election materials to the polling units, some of the personnel of the union (with reference to drivers) sometimes deliberately show up late to their duty post, while some are absent on election day. The reason for some of these challenges, according to the study, is that some of the drivers complain that they are offered meagre sums by the executives of the union, who acted as the channel between the personnel of the union and INEC. The implication of the foregoing, as revealed by the study, is traceable to delays in the commencement of elections. Ajala (2019) argues that elections in Nigeria, which are scheduled to commence early on the day of elections are often marred by delays in the arrival of electoral materials and INEC staff. Consequently, Otoibhi, Abolade and Abe (2022) believe that delays in the commencement of election due to the late arrival of election materials is one of the factors negatively impacting on electoral process in Nigeria, leading to political apathy.

Also, the study discovers that some members of the NURTW are being deployed by political elites to disrupt elections, thereby impacting negatively on the outcome of elections. This, according to the study, is the factor responsible for the prevalence of electoral violence in the country such as ballot box snatching, stuffing, voters' intimidation, among other occurrences affecting the credibility of the electoral process (Ogunde, 2022). Odunsi (2019) and Yujo (2019) contended that politicians sought the support of interest groups such as the NURTW during campaigns in order to influence the outcome of the electoral process. Odunsi (2019) believed that exchange of votes

for cash was one of the many challenges negatively affecting electoral process in the country. Hence, politicians on many accounts bought their ways into public offices. This was made easy by the poor socioeconomic condition of the electorates.

In the views of Omobowale and Fayiga (2017), politicians and leaders of their party monetised electoral process due to the prevalence of poverty in the country. This explains why political thugs adopted violence as a means to ensure that their patrons (persons seeking public offices) take over the rein of government. This position supports the patron-client theory, another theoretical framework of analysis adopted for the study, which states that tradeoff often takes place between political actors and their supporters within the polity. This position was supported by Yujo (2019), who also advanced that most elections conducted in Nigeria across levels of government had been characterised by different controversies sometimes leading to the cancellation of the election. During the 2019 general elections, for instance, INEC had to cancel elections conducted in some polling units in Lagos, Anambra, Rivers states due to electoral violence, which led to the burning of ballot papers (Yujo, 2019).

It may be argued that due to the nature of their venture, which allows most members of the union to interface with people at the grassroot vis-à-vis transporting people and goods from one part of the state to another, as well as the support members of the NURTW enjoy from the state government where they operate in, take for instance, Lagos, they are often used as instruments of coercion to achieve the political ambitions of their patrons. Hence, free, fair and credible elections may be an impossible feat to achieve in Nigeria. These acts, if not checked, have the capacity to further drive Nigeria's democracy to the mud, thereby impacting negatively on the electoral process in the country.

Findings on the third objective of the study, which investigated whether there was a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different state branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the electoral process revealed that the nature of the transport union in the Southwest

vis-à-vis its leadership structure and modes of operations made it nearly impossible to advance uniformity in their involvement in elections in the country. This, according to the study, emanated from the different tactics adopted by the leadership of the different state branches of the transport union as well as units (factions) that existed within the union. Evelyn (2022) argued that on many occasions, violent conflicts broke out between factions within the transport union leading to the death of commuters and destruction of property. These conflicts were often borne out of leadership tussles, and differences in ideologies that exist within the organisation. Recently, Musiliu Akinsanya, popularly referred to as Mc Oluomo was suspended by the national body of NURTW for acts of insubordination and misconduct (Opejobi, 2022). This buttressed the lack of cohesion and leadership tussle within the union.

The power of the state government over the operations of the union as well as the differences in the political parties ruling the states in the Southwest should be reckoned with. The challenge with the foregoing, according to the study, was that conflicts and disagreements were inevitable within the union. Hence, the majority of the views expressed in the study revealed that the leadership of the transport union in the Southwest, given the differences in the political parties that control the helms of political affairs in the different states in the Southwest, take for instance, Oyo State ruled by the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP), Lagos (APC) and Ondo state (APC) made it difficult for a collective endorsement of persons seeking public office in the states in the Southwest. This explains the tendency of the state government to dissolve or even suspend the operations of the transport union in the state at will. This compels each state branch of the transport union to throw its weight behind the ruling party in the state where they operate. These factors, according to the study, made it nearly impossible to achieve cohesion vis-à-vis the union's involvement in electoral process in the Southwest. Drawing from the foregoing, Ogidan (2022) states that due to incessant

violent clashes between factions of the NURTW or with security operatives, the state government where this union operates have had to suspend their operations. For instance, on January 17, 2022, violent clashes between members of the NURTW and Police officers in Oyo State left more than ten (10) police officers sustaining fatal injuries. This led to the suspension of the operations of the NURTW in Oyo State and its replacement with a new transport union— Park Management Services (PMS). The same situation caused the Lagos State government to temporarily suspend the operations of the transport union following the conflict within the NURTW, which led to the suspension of the state Chairman, Musiliu Akinsanya otherwise known as MC Oluomo by the national body of the union (Ogidan, 2022).

The above position was corroborated by Aliyu (2022), who contended that one of the factors affecting the operations of the NURTW was traceable to the influence of the state government over the affairs of the transport union. This implied that if the union failed to support the ruling political party in the state, it might lead to their suspension or proscription. Hence, they were often compelled to endorse/support the ruling party of the state.

Also, the study discovers that the involvement of the NURTW in election vis-à-vis the MoU it signed with INEC arguably necessitates some level of uniformity in the operations of the union in carrying out its logistics roles (transport of election materials and INEC staff) during election. This, according to the views expressed largely by INEC officials, reveals that INEC interfaces with the national leadership of the transport union, who thereafter communicates the agreement and modes of operations during the election to the state branches. This underscores some degree of strong leadership structure and hierarchy within the transport union.

The foregoing views are reinforced by Nyamnjoh (2017) and Moncada (2016), who argued that interest groups across the world use its leadership structure and tactics as instruments to achieve

the goals of its members. Gatt and Owen (2018) further stress that although there often arise areas of conflicts within the workings and operations of interest groups; one of the areas of strength of interest groups was their quest to achieve the interest of their members. This goal, according to Bayero (2016), may be impossible to achieve if these interest groups lacked a strong leadership structure. The study also submits (though may not be tied to electoral process) that one of the uniformities of the NURTW is traceable to the colour of their uniform (green and white) and the fact that they are charged with collection of tolls/levies from individuals, who engaged in public transportation within the state (vehicles, motorcycle and tricycles alike). The uniform of the NURTW represents the colour of the country's national flag, which is a symbol of nationalism within the workings of the transport union.

Findings on the fourth objective of the study, which seeks to ascertain how electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening democratic process in the country show that one of the factors impeding electoral process in the country is lack of transparency in elections, which manifests in areas such as cancellation of votes in some polling units, ballot boxing snatching, intimidation and harassment of voters, violent clashes between individuals and groups loyal to persons seeking public office and political parties, among other manifestations that are antithetical to elections in the country. Hence, the need for INEC to promote transparent elections by adopting and applying functional and effective technology to the electoral process. Although INEC has since 2015 (in a bid promote credible elections in the country) adopted technology such as the smart card readers (SCRs) and most recently the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS), which was first used in Nigeria in September 11, 2021 during the Isoko-South I State Constituency Bye-election in Delta State and subsequently during the 2021

gubernatorial election in Anambra State, these technologies have been marred with technical glitches (Ojochogu, 2022).

According to the British Broadcasting Corporation (2021), the introduction of the BVAS as a replacement to the SCRs was a step in the right direction in the quest to attaining credible and transparent elections in Nigeria; however, technical glitches associated with the usage of the technology in the Anambra State election questioned INEC's level of preparedness at ensuring credible elections in the country, which has since 1999 contended with issues associated with electoral malpractices. This development underscored the structural-functional theory adopted for the study, which stated that some structures were established within the polity to perform certain function. The use of technology introduced by INEC lends credence to their 'function' of promoting credible elections in the country. Oguntola, Isuwa, Obeta and Igbekoyi (2021) state that some of the drawbacks witnessed during elections in Nigeria are often traceable to the non-functionality of the use of technology. This, according to them, is responsible for the delays witnessed during election, which has the tendency to breed political apathy. It is argued, therefore, that although the adoption of technology in electoral process in Nigeria has witnessed drawbacks, it is an instrumental means by which credible electoral process may be achieved in Nigeria, particularly inferring from democratic states across the world such as the U.S., UK, France among other developed countries in Europe leveraging on technology to conduct elections.

The study also finds that amending the Electoral Act, which has the potential to promote political participation and credibility of elections in the country is a key process that will enhance voters' confidence in the electoral process. President Muhammadu Buhari's eventual assent to the 2022 Electoral Act (Amendment) Bill on February 25, 2022, is noteworthy. Some of the provisions of the Electoral Act include the digitalisation of electoral process vis-à-vis electronic voting and

transmission of election results, timelines for campaigns and candidates' nomination, review of election results declared under duress (Cyril, 2022). Igbohor (2019) notes that the amendments made to the Electoral Act will serve as a conduit towards correcting some of the anomalies that have characterised the electoral process in Nigeria, especially issues surrounding electronic voting and transmission of election results. Olowolagba (2022) describes the signing of the 2022 Electoral Act (Amendment) Bill as victory for democratic and electoral process in Nigeria. This will not only ensure a broad participation in the electoral process, but also promote transparency and credibility at the polls.

The study also establishes that one of the factors that if addressed has the capacity to enhance voters' confidence in Nigeria is electoral violence, which is often carried out by persons loyal to public office seekers and political parties. Odo (2015) asserts that the major factor driving political apathy in Nigeria is violence often experienced at the polls. This, according to the author, has led to the death of many persons while trying to exercise their civil obligation. Similarly, Campbell (2010) subscribes to the fact that violence experienced during elections in Nigeria is one of the major challenges negatively impacting on the country's quest to deepening its democratic practice.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Summary

The study examined the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) and Electoral Process in Southwest, Nigeria (2015-2020). This was with the specific objectives of identifying ways in which the NURTW informally gets involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria; ascertain the implications of the activities of the NURTW on the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria; investigate whether there was a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different State branches of the NURTW vis-à-vis their involvement in the electoral process; and examine how the electoral process in Nigeria might be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening democratic process in the country.

Data for the study were gathered through primary and secondary sources. Primary data were sourced via in-depth interview of 50 key informant respondents (KIRs), which comprises personnel from the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) and National Union of Road Transport Workers (NUTRW), academics from Nigerian universities, card carrying members of the All Progressives Congress (APC) and the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP) as well as commuters and electorates. Secondary data sources included books, journal articles, online publications, newspaper editorials, published and unpublished dissertation and via the internet. The data gathered were analysed through thematic analysis.

6.2 Findings of the Study

The study found that NURTW was saddled with the formal responsibility of providing logistics services for the transportation of election materials to different polling units in the country following the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) INEC and NURTW signed on the 15th of January 2015. The study also found that the status of the NURTW prevented the union as an interest

group from the public show of support to political parties and politicians. Hence, members of the transport union were expected to be politically neutral but can individually support and be members of political parties. This position was, however, disregarded on the ground that the leadership of the NURTW, particularly in Lagos State and other Southwestern states have on many accounts publicly endorsed political parties.

Furthermore, the study also found that some Nigerians were not aware that INEC signed a MoU with transport unions in Nigeria to act as a support system in providing logistics during the conduct of elections in the country. This perhaps underscored why some electorates demonstrated ambivalent attitudes towards voting due to their primordial notion that the involvement of the NURTW members would compromise the credibility of the electoral process. Hence, political apathy was displayed by these electorates. The study found that despite involving the NURTW in transporting election materials to polling units, some of the personnel of the union (with reference to drivers) sometimes deliberately showed up late to their duty post while some were absent on election day. The reason was due to the meagre sums these drivers were offered by the executives of the union, who acted as the channel between the NURTW and INEC.

Similarly, some members of the NURTW were being deployed by political elites to disrupt elections before, during and after elections, thereby impacting negatively on the outcome of elections. This was one of the factors responsible for the prevalence of electoral violence in the country leading to ballot box snatching, voters' intimidation among other outcomes affecting the credibility of the electoral process.

The study also revealed that the nature of the transport union in the Southwest vis-à-vis its leadership structure and modes of operations made it impossible to achieve uniformity in their involvement in elections in the country. This was due to the difference in tactics adopted by the

leadership of the different state branches of the transport union. The study also discovered that the state governors wielded authority over the workings and operations of the union, which often led to the suspension of the union at the slightest provocations or crisis within the union. The study also established that the use of technology in the electoral process during voters' registration and on the day of election would play a key role in checking the issues relating to electoral malpractices during elections in the country.

6.3 Conclusion

The study concluded that through the logistics roles the National Union of Road Transport Union (NURTW) played during elections in Nigeria, the union had contributed its quota towards deepening democratic practice in the country. This substantiated the position that the electoral process would be more effective when relevant stakeholders and the electoral management body (EMB) charted a common course aimed at promoting electoral credibility thereby deepening democratic practice in the country.

6.4 Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

While it is an established fact that electoral process in a democratic state thrived through the contributions of relevant stakeholders as was the case of the NURTW, it is recommended that INEC should scrutinize and orientate personnel of the NURTW that will be involved in conveying election materials and INEC staff on the day of election. This will prevent circumstances such as delays in the arrival of election materials, and other forms of sharp practices that could negatively affect election.

Although the use of technology in election has been acknowledged as one of the ways of ensuring transparency at the polls, it is recommended that INEC should properly test run the gadgets to be

used on election day in order to be on top of possible technical glitches that may arise during elections.

Additionally, disorderly conduct such as the use of political thugs to disrupt elections as criminalized in Section 125 of the Electoral Act 2022 should be strictly upheld such that perpetrators or political parties found wanting are convicted to a maximum fine of N500,000 or imprisonment for a term of 12 months or both. This will play a key role in abating electoral violence as well as voters' apathy in the country.

Similarly, it is recommended that security personnel deployed to different polling units should be made to live up to expectations by ensuring orderliness and peaceful voting exercise and not to intimidate or harass the electorates.

With reference to voters' registration exercise, it is recommended that INEC develops a software that will advance the ease of the registration exercise through the use of mobile phones, and collections of the permanent voters' card (PVC) should be made easy at INEC offices across the states of the federation. This will increase the numbers of electorates eligible to vote.

6.5 Limitation of Study

The study was not without some limitations. One of the major factors that posed as a limitation to the study hinged on the inability of the researcher to interview, the then Chairman of NURTW, Lagos Chapter (now Chairman of Lagos Parks Management Committee), Musiliu Akinsanya popularly called MC Oluomo, despite repeated visits to his office. Also, some respondents declined having the interview session recorded, thereby making the researcher resort to taking notes, which, in comparison with audio recording is arguably not comprehensive. Other limitations of the study revolved around some other respondents declining to be interviewed. Despite the foregoing limitations, the study achieved its objectives, and as such contributed to advancing the frontiers of knowledge on the subject of the study.

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APPENDIX I

**OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE-IFE, NIGERIA.
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES,
DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL SCIENCE.**

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Dear Respondents,

I am a postgraduate student of the above-named university and department conducting a study titled: **National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) and Electoral Process in Southwest, Nigeria (2015-2020)**, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Science in Political Science.

Be informed that your response is strictly for academic purpose and as such your identity and comments will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

The following questions will guide the study:

1. What is your view on the performance of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) in Nigeria?
2. Drawing from your response to the above question, are you aware that the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) participates in the electoral process in Nigeria?
3. If yes, in what ways, in your opinion, do the NURTW informally get involved in the electoral process in Southwest, Nigeria?
4. What do you see as the implications of the activities of the NURTW on the electoral process particularly in Southwest, Nigeria?
5. Is there, in your opinion, a uniformity of perspective and approach among the different State branches of the NURTW in involving in the electoral process?
6. How do you think the electoral process in Nigeria may be enhanced to improve voters' confidence thereby deepening the country's quest for credible election in Southwest, Nigeria?
7. Any more comments?

Information on the Key Informant Respondents (KIRs).

The table below revealed the information on the key respondents' informants selected for the study.

S/N	Names of KIRs	Institutional Affiliation	Rank/Status	Location of Interview
1	Lukmon Ikotun	NURTW	Executive	Osogbo
2	Mariam Babatunde	NURTW	Executive	Osogbo
3	Abegunrin Saheed	NURTW	Executive	Osogbo
4	Tajudeen Olusola	NURTW	Personnel	Osogbo
5	Julius Adeolu	NURTW	Personnel	Osogbo
6	Omololu Ibidun	NURTW	Personnel	Osogbo
7	Ogunwande Jumoke	NURTW	Personnel	Osogbo
8	Femi Oloruntoba	NURTW	Executive	Akure
9	Isaac Adebayo	NURTW	Executive	Akure
10	Niran Adegoke	NURTW	Personnel	Akure
11	Sunkanmi Afolabi	NURTW	Personnel	Akure
12	Inofia Frank	NURTW	Personnel	Akure
13	Macauley Ogun	NURTW	Personnel	Akure
14	Akintoju Samuel	NURTW	Personnel	Akure
15	Olabanji Qaasim	NURTW	Personnel	Ikeja
16	Idris Ajibola	NURTW	Personnel	Ikeja
17	Iraboh Mark	NURTW	Personnel	Oshodi
18	Omoju Greg	NURTW	Personnel	Oshodi

19	Braimah Jude	NURTW	Personnel	Ilupeju
20	Ogoloto Bamise	NURTW	Personnel	Ikeja
21	Sylvester Nnam	NURTW	Personnel	Ikeja
22	Charles Omoraka	INEC	Personnel	Akure
23	Alhaji Somuyiwa	INEC	Personnel	Akure
24	Dare Adeyemo	INEC	Personnel	Akure
25	Wale Oyaleye.	INEC	Personnel	Akure
25	Femi Agunniyi.	INEC	Personnel	Akure
26	Mr Qadri Adetunji	INEC	Personnel	Osogbo
27	Eyinaya Chinedu	INEC	Personnel	Osogbo
28	Zoe Adeomi	INEC	Personnel	Osogbo
29	Olusola Tajudeen	INEC	Personnel	Osogbo
30	Adegbite Sarah	INEC	Personnel	Osogbo
31	Alfred Theodore	INEC	Personnel	Surulere
32	Omolafe Tobi	INEC	Personnel	Surulere
33	Ogunleye Eleshinloye	INEC	Personnel	Surulere
34	Osifeso Rita	INEC	Personnel	Surulere
35	Omole Mark	INEC	Personnel	Surulere
36	Dr Yakeen R. A.	Lagos State University	Lecturer	Lagos
37	Dr Banye C. A.	Lagos State University	Lecturer	Lagos
38	Dr Olorunimbe Rafiu	Lagos State University	Lecturer	Lagos
39	Okunlola Ridwat	Peoples Democratic Party	Member	Osun state

40	Mr. Albert	Peoples Democratic Party	Member	Ondo state
41	Makinde Ojo	Peoples Democratic Party	Member	Lagos state
42	Oseni Azeez	All Progressive Congress	Member	Osun state
43	Adebowale Miftau	All Progressive Congress	Member	Lagos state
44	Saheed Abegunrin	All Progressive Congress	Member	Osun state
45	Oladokun Mutiu	Electorate/Commuter	-	Ondo state
46	Lukmon	Electorate/Commuter	-	Osun state
47	Ayodele	Electorate/Commuter	-	Ondo state
48	Femi	Electorate/Commuter	-	Ondo state
49	Damola	Electorate/Commuter	-	Lagos state
50	Ibitolu John	Electorate/Commuter	-	Lagos state

Source: Author's compilation.

APPENDIX II

1. Interview with Respondent 1 conducted on the 18/01/2022
2. Interview with Respondent 2 conducted on the 18/01/2022
3. Interview with Respondent 3 conducted on the 19/01/2022
4. Interview with Respondent 4 conducted on the 21/01/2022
5. Interview with Respondent 5 conducted on the 20/01/2022
6. Interview with Respondent 6 conducted on the 19/01/2022
7. Interview with Respondent 7 conducted on the 25/01/2022
8. Interview with Respondent 8 conducted on the 27/01/2022
9. Interview with Respondent 9 conducted on the 25/01/2022
10. Interview with Respondent 10 conducted on the 30/01/2022
11. Interview with Respondent 11 conducted on the 30/01/2022
12. Interview with Respondent 12 conducted on the 31/01/2022
13. Interview with Respondent 13 conducted on the 2/02/2022
14. Interview with Respondent 14 conducted on the 4/02/2022
15. Interview with Respondent 15 conducted on the 5/02/2022
16. Interview with Respondent 16 conducted on the 6/02/2022
17. Interview with Respondent 17 conducted on the 5/02/2022
18. Interview with Respondent 18 conducted on the 5/02/2022
19. Interview with Respondent 19 conducted on the 5/02/2022
20. Interview with Respondent 20 conducted on the 8/02/2022
21. Interview with Respondent 21 conducted on the 22/02/2022
22. Interview with Respondent 22 conducted on the 22/02/2022
23. Interview with Respondent 23 conducted on the 13/02/2022
24. Interview with Respondent 24 conducted on the 11/02/2022
25. Interview with Respondent 25 conducted on the 13/02/2022
26. Interview with Respondent 26 conducted on the 11/02/2022
27. Interview with Respondent 27 conducted on the 22/01/2022
28. Interview with Respondent 28 conducted on the 18/01/2022
29. Interview with Respondent 29 conducted on the 17/02/2022
30. Interview with Respondent 30 conducted on the 18/02/2022
31. Interview with Respondent 31 conducted on the 25/01/2022
32. Interview with Respondent 32 conducted on the 19/02/2022
33. Interview with Respondent 33 conducted on the 19/01/2022
34. Interview with Respondent 34 conducted on the 23/02/2022
35. Interview with Respondent 35 conducted on the 24/02/2022
36. Interview with Respondent 36 conducted on the 18/02/2022
37. Interview with Respondent 37 conducted on the 16/01/2022
38. Interview with Respondent 38 conducted on the 4/02/2022
39. Interview with Respondent 39 conducted on the 5/02/2022

40. Interview with Respondent 40 conducted on the 20/02/2022
41. Interview with Respondent 41 conducted on the 19/01/2022
42. Interview with Respondent 42 conducted on the 24/01/2022
43. Interview with Respondent 43 conducted on the 23/02/2022
44. Interview with Respondent 44 conducted on the 31/01/2022
45. Interview with Respondent 45 conducted on the 11/02/2022
46. Interview with Respondent 46 conducted on the 12/02/2022
47. Interview with Respondent 47 conducted on the 11/02/2022
48. Interview with Respondent 48 conducted on the 11/01/2022
49. Interview with Respondent 49 conducted on the 14/01/2022
50. Interview with Respondent 50 conducted on the 13/01/2022
51. Interview with Respondent 51 conducted on the 18/01/2022
52. Interview with Respondent 52 conducted on the 18/01/2022
53. Interview with Respondent 53 conducted on the 19/01/2022
54. Interview with Respondent 54 conducted on the 21/01/2022
55. Interview with Respondent 55 conducted on the 20/01/2022
56. Interview with Respondent 56 conducted on the 19/01/2022
57. Interview with Respondent 57 conducted on the 25/01/2022
58. Interview with Respondent 58 conducted on the 27/01/2022
59. Interview with Respondent 59 conducted on the 25/01/2022
60. Interview with Respondent 60 conducted on the 30/01/2022
61. Interview with Respondent 61 conducted on the 30/01/2022
62. Interview with Respondent 62 conducted on the 31/01/2022
63. Interview with Respondent 63 conducted on the 2/02/2022
64. Interview with Respondent 64 conducted on the 4/02/2022
65. Interview with Respondent 65 conducted on the 5/02/2022
66. Interview with Respondent 66 conducted on the 6/02/2022
67. Interview with Respondent 67 conducted on the 5/02/2022
68. Interview with Respondent 68 conducted on the 5/02/2022
69. Interview with Respondent 69 conducted on the 5/02/2022
70. Interview with Respondent 70 conducted on the 8/02/2022
71. Interview with Respondent 71 conducted on the 22/02/2022
72. Interview with Respondent 72 conducted on the 22/02/2022
73. Interview with Respondent 73 conducted on the 13/02/2022
74. Interview with Respondent 74 conducted on the 11/02/2022
75. Interview with Respondent 75 conducted on the 13/02/2022
76. Interview with Respondent 76 conducted on the 11/02/2022
77. Interview with Respondent 77 conducted on the 22/01/2022
78. Interview with Respondent 78 conducted on the 18/01/2022
79. Interview with Respondent 79 conducted on the 17/02/2022

80. Interview with Respondent 80 conducted on the 18/02/2022
81. Interview with Respondent 81 conducted on the 25/01/2022
82. Interview with Respondent 82 conducted on the 19/02/2022
83. Interview with Respondent 83 conducted on the 19/01/2022
84. Interview with Respondent 84 conducted on the 23/02/2022
85. Interview with Respondent 85 conducted on the 24/02/2022
86. Interview with Respondent 86 conducted on the 18/02/2022
87. Interview with Respondent 87 conducted on the 16/01/2022
88. Interview with Respondent 88 conducted on the 4/02/2022
89. Interview with Respondent 89 conducted on the 5/02/2022
90. Interview with Respondent 90 conducted on the 20/02/2022
91. Interview with Respondent 91 conducted on the 19/01/2022
92. Interview with Respondent 92 conducted on the 24/01/2022
93. Interview with Respondent 93 conducted on the 23/02/2022
94. Interview with Respondent 94 conducted on the 31/01/2022
95. Interview with Respondent 95 conducted on the 11/02/2022
96. Interview with Respondent 96 conducted on the 12/02/2022
97. Interview with Respondent 97 conducted on the 11/02/2022
98. Interview with Respondent 98 conducted on the 11/01/2022
99. Interview with Respondent 99 conducted on the 14/01/2022
100. Interview with Respondent 100 conducted on the 13/01/2022
101. Interview with Respondent 101 conducted on the 18/01/2022
102. Interview with Respondent 102 conducted on the 18/01/2022
103. Interview with Respondent 103 conducted on the 19/01/2022
104. Interview with Respondent 104 conducted on the 21/01/2022
105. Interview with Respondent 105 conducted on the 20/01/2022
106. Interview with Respondent 106 conducted on the 19/01/2022
107. Interview with Respondent 107 conducted on the 25/01/2022
108. Interview with Respondent 108 conducted on the 27/01/2022
109. Interview with Respondent 109 conducted on the 25/01/2022
110. Interview with Respondent 110 conducted on the 30/01/2022
111. Interview with Respondent 111 conducted on the 30/01/2022
112. Interview with Respondent 112 conducted on the 31/01/2022
113. Interview with Respondent 113 conducted on the 2/02/2022
114. Interview with Respondent 114 conducted on the 4/02/2022
115. Interview with Respondent 115 conducted on the 5/02/2022
116. Interview with Respondent 116 conducted on the 6/02/2022
117. Interview with Respondent 117 conducted on the 5/02/2022
118. Interview with Respondent 118 conducted on the 5/02/2022
119. Interview with Respondent 119 conducted on the 5/02/2022

120. Interview with Respondent 120 conducted on the 8/02/2022
121. Interview with Respondent 121 conducted on the 22/02/2022
122. Interview with Respondent 122 conducted on the 22/02/2022
123. Interview with Respondent 123 conducted on the 13/02/2022
124. Interview with Respondent 124 conducted on the 11/02/2022
125. Interview with Respondent 125 conducted on the 13/02/2022
126. Interview with Respondent 126 conducted on the 11/02/2022
127. Interview with Respondent 127 conducted on the 22/01/2022
128. Interview with Respondent 128 conducted on the 18/01/2022
129. Interview with Respondent 129 conducted on the 17/02/2022
130. Interview with Respondent 130 conducted on the 18/02/2022
131. Interview with Respondent 131 conducted on the 25/01/2022
132. Interview with Respondent 132 conducted on the 19/02/2022
133. Interview with Respondent 133 conducted on the 19/01/2022